

D2.2 Blueprint of port call processes

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Abbreviations

AIS	Automatic Identification System	MIRA	Maritime ICT Reference Architecture
API	Application Programming Interfaces	MSW	Maritime Single Window
ATA	Actual Time of Arrival	NAV	Navtor
ATC	Actual Time of Completion	NOR	Notice of Readiness
ATD	Actual Time of Departure	NSP	Nautical Service Provider
ATS	Actual Time of Start	OV	Operational Viewpoint
BIMCO	Baltic and International Maritime Council	P3C	Port Call Coordination Centre
BPMN	Business Process Model and Notation	PBP	Pilot Boarding Place
CSP	Cargo Service Provider	PCO	Port Call Optimisation
DCSA	Digital Container Shipping Association	PCS	Port Community System
DMN	Decision Model and Notation	PPA	Port passage Planning area
EMSWe	European Maritime Single Window environment	PTA	Planned Time of Arrival
EOSP	End of Sea Passage	PTC	Planned Time of Completion
ETA	Estimated Time of Arrival	PTD	Planned Time of Departure
ETC	Estimated Time of Completion	PTS	Planned Time of Start
ETD	Estimated Time of Departure	RTA	Requested Time of Arrival
ETS	Estimated Time of Start	RTC	Requested Time of Completion
FAL	Facilitation	RTD	Requested Time of Departure
FAOP	Full Away on Passage	RTS	Requested Time of Start
FIFO	First-In-First-Out	SDU	University of Southern Denmark
FL	FixLog	SO	Sintef Ocean
GEF	Global Environment Facility	SOLAS	International Convention for Safety of Life at Sea
GIA	Global Industry Alliance	STMB	Single Terminal, Multiple Berthing-Protocol
GloMEEP	Global Maritime Energy Efficiency Partnerships	STSB	Single Terminal, Single Berthing
IAPH	International Association of Ports and Harbors	SSP	Ship Service Provider
ICT	Information Communications Technology	TIC40	Terminal Industry Committee 4.0
IMO	International Maritime Organization	UAF	Unified Architecture Framework
ISM	International Safety Management	UN/CEFACT	United Nations Centre for Trade Facilitation and Electronic Business
ISO	International Organization for Standardization	UNDP	United Nations Development Programme
ITSN	ITS Norway	VHF	Very High Frequency
JIT	Just-in-Time	VTA	Virtual Time of Arrival
KPI	Key Performance Indicator	VTS	Vessel Traffic Services
MARPOL	International Convention for the Prevention of Pollution Ships		

Executive Summary

The port call process constitutes a critical element of maritime supply chains and plays a pivotal role in shaping their overall efficiency, environmental performance, and long-term viability. Against the backdrop of increasing demands for sustainability, economic efficiency, and technological advancement, it has become essential to systematically evaluate existing operational procedures and to identify targeted areas for improvement.

Within the framework of the DYNAPORT project, deliverable *D2.2 Blueprint of Port Call Process* aims to develop a comprehensive target model for an idealised port call process. This blueprint is intended to demonstrate how future port calls can be designed to be more efficient, sustainable, and resilient. In doing so, it considers both the prevailing operational conditions in selected partner ports and the technical solutions already devised within the project.

The conceptual foundation of this target model is provided by deliverable *D2.1*, which assessed the current state of port call processes across a range of ports. This assessment was based on on-site investigations and sought to identify operational challenges, capacity constraints, and systemic barriers. The findings revealed that the nature and extent of these issues are closely linked to the type of port and its infrastructural configuration. At the same time, a number of common challenges were identified across multiple locations, primarily relating to systemic and infrastructural deficiencies. These included a lack of standardised procedures, limited harmonisation of operational processes across stakeholders, and insufficient integration of information flows.

In addition to these cross-cutting issues, port-specific challenges were also observed. These included regulatory constraints unique to particular ports, and divergent stakeholder interests, both of which were found to significantly impede the smooth coordination of port call operations.

As part of deliverable *D2.1*, several potential solutions were proposed. Among these were the introduction of standardised communication and coordination mechanisms between stakeholders, the optimisation of logistical workflows, and the harmonisation of technical and infrastructural systems across ports.

The insights derived from *D2.1* form the basis for the elaboration of the target model in *D2.2*. Building upon the comprehensive assessment of the current state, *D2.2* develops an ideal-type port call concept that integrates modern technologies and optimised operational procedures. The overarching objective is to enhance the efficiency, sustainability, and resilience of port logistics systems. Central to this effort is the development of a practical and forward-looking blueprint that offers concrete recommendations for overcoming the challenges identified in the earlier analysis.

Given the heterogeneous organisational structures of seaports and the increasing complexity of port operations, particularly at larger sites with multiple stakeholders, the conceptual focus was placed on developing a transferable blueprint. The aim is to provide a structured target concept that can be flexibly applied across ports of varying sizes and characteristics. This allows the proposed measures to be adapted to local conditions and gradually integrated into existing operational processes.

At the core of this approach is not only the depiction of an idealised port call process. The blueprint also explicitly considers the diversity of port types and their specific organisational and

operational conditions. In doing so, it enables port authorities and associated actors to implement targeted solutions that address local requirements while contributing to overarching objectives such as increased efficiency, transparency and sustainability.

To enhance both the transferability and practical applicability of the concept, the blueprint is structured into three functional layers: The Contracts and Regulations Layer, the P3C Layer (Port Call Coordination Centre), and the Operations Layer. This tripartite structure reflects the different dimensions of the port call process and provides a transparent framework for modular implementation.

- The Contracts and Regulations Layer forms the legal and normative foundation. It encompasses national legislation, international regulations, bilateral agreements, and contractual frameworks between port authorities, shipping companies, and other stakeholders. This layer ensures that the blueprint can be implemented in compliance with existing legal structures while allowing room for context-specific adaptation.
- The P3C Layer serves as the communication and coordination hub for the port call process. This layer involves the collection, processing and distribution of information related to planned and ongoing ship arrivals. As a digital communication platform, the P3C ensures that all relevant parties – including port authorities, pilots, terminal operators and service providers – have access to consistent, up-to-date and relevant information. This contributes significantly to reducing uncertainty, avoiding waiting times and optimising resource allocation.
- The Operations Layer represents the practical level where port call processes are executed. It contains concrete recommendations, standardised procedures and technical interface solutions that can be directly applied in day-to-day operations. As such, this layer bridges the gap between strategic concept development and practical implementation.

This layered structure not only enhances the conceptual clarity of the blueprint, but also facilitates its systematic and scalable application. Depending on the development stage, scale and strategic orientation of a given port, individual layers can be prioritised or jointly developed. In this way, the blueprint becomes a flexible tool that accommodates the complex realities of modern port logistics, while providing a shared reference framework for improved coordination, transparency and operational efficiency.

To further advance the realisation of the blueprint, a set of complementary strategies and methods is proposed, addressing both the institutional and operational dimensions of implementation. These strategies range from the contractual level to the organisational, technological, and procedural domains.

At the technological level, the integration of interoperable data architectures, standardised port call protocols, and secure digital infrastructures ensures a consistent, reliable, and timely flow of information among all actors.

At the procedural level, mechanisms such as timeslot allocation, Estimated Time of Arrival (ETA) monitoring and updating, the dynamic adjustment of service sequencing and resource scheduling, as well as the consistent use of standardised time stamps, enable precise, transparent, and coordinated management of port call operations. Continuous updating of time

stamps helps to reduce planning uncertainty, anticipate bottlenecks, and optimise operational decision-making in real time. In addition, iterative evaluation mechanisms, feedback loops, and performance metrics contribute to a learning-oriented, data-driven improvement process.

In summary, these strategies and methods constitute a comprehensive pathway for realisation that complements the structural design of the blueprint. They ensure that its conceptual robustness is matched by practical feasibility and international interoperability, thereby supporting sustainable transformation across contractual, organisational, and operational contexts.

In the subsequent project phase, the blueprint developed in this deliverable will serve as the basis in particular for deliverable *D6.2 Integrated Simulation and KPI Development*. In this deliverable, a set of operational scenarios will be defined for medium-sized to large ports. These scenarios are intended to model various operating conditions and optimisation measures. By applying predefined Key Performance Indicators (KPIs), the effectiveness of the proposed solutions in improving port call performance will be quantitatively assessed. The simulation-based approach will enable a robust evaluation of the potential impacts under realistic conditions, thereby supporting evidence-based decision-making.

1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose of the document

This document describes the target state of the port call based on the results collected in the *HORIZON-CL5-2023-D5-01 Innovation Action project DYNAPORT Deliverables D2.1 Description of port call processes*. As described in the grant agreement, this document therefore represents the result *D2.2 Blueprint of port call process*.

D2.2 provides a systematic identification and description of to-be processes and interactions between the various actors in the port call, considering the challenges and potential for improvement identified in the International Taskforce Port Call Optimization (ITPCO), the Digital Container Shipping Association (DCSA) and the on-site studies in *D2.1 Description of port call processes* and *D3.1 Multi-party cooperation and goal alignment for voyage optimisation in combination with JIT port call*. As a result, the deliverables *D2.1* and *D3.1* form one of the central foundations for the development of the blueprint for optimising the port call process in *D2.2*.

The objective of *D2.2* is to develop a generic blueprint that can be used as an operational roadmap for the further standardisation of port calls. The blueprint can be used to increase process transparency through visualisation, identify the interfaces between different stakeholders, optimise processes by uncovering issues and sources of error and thus serve as a basis for redesigning processes. For this purpose, an optimised to-be process is modelled in a systematic approach.

The blueprint for integrated port cooperation contributes to and shapes other important research and development activities within the DYNAPORT project. The planning and realisation of demonstrations are also based on the blueprint and the associated Research and Development activities.

1.2 Intended readership

The intended audience of the document is the general public.

1.3 Structure of this document

This subchapter provides an overview of the content in the individual chapters.

- Chapter 1 is an introductory chapter describing the purpose of the document, the intended readership, and the structure of the document. It also highlights the stakeholder involvement and outlines the relationships to other projects, initiatives, and deliverables within the DYNAPORT project.
- Chapter 2 provides the theoretical background, starting with the definition of the blueprint. It continues with an in-depth description of the port call process, including the process steps, involved stakeholders, time stamps, communication flows, and contracts and agreements.
- Chapter 3 presents the current situation of port call processes by summarizing the main challenges identified in previous work, highlighting deviations from the proposed

International Maritime Organization (IMO) port call process, and discussing potential improvements through Just-In-Time (JIT) arrival concepts.

- Chapter 4 outlines the methodology applied in the development and analysis of the blueprint and port call processes.
- Chapter 5 provides the blueprint of port call processes. It includes the design of the blueprint with its three layers (contracts and regulations, P3C, operations), as well as a detailed breakdown of the port call phases: pre-arrival, port arrival, berth visit, port departure, and strategies for implementation.
- Chapter 6 concludes the document by summarizing the findings of the deliverable, reflecting on key results, achievements, and defining next steps within the project.

1.4 Stakeholder involvement

Deliverable *D2.2 Blueprint of port call processes* has been developed in close collaboration with several relevant consortium partners and partners from the sister project MISSION. This collaboration made it possible to incorporate different perspectives and technical expertise into the development of this important deliverable. The stakeholders involved contributed by developing basic theoretical content, identifying specific challenges in the context of the port call process and providing further insights to improve the process.

In addition to the theoretical foundation, practical elements have been considered, which made it possible to analyse and further develop the port call process from different perspectives. The contributions of the stakeholders were therefore a decisive component in the creation of a comprehensive and practically relevant blueprint.

The following members of the DYNAPORT project consortium and MISSION project consortium contributed significantly to *D2.2*:

- DYNAPORT: FixLog (FL)
- DYNAPORT: Sintef (SO)
- DYNAPORT: ITS Norway (ITSN)
- DYNAPORT: NAVTOR (NAV)
- DYNAPORT: Port of Sines (CPLS)
- MISSION: Terminal Industry Committee 4.0 (TIC40)

These partners have played a central role in the collection of data, the analysis of existing processes and the formulation of recommendations for action that can be implemented within the scope of optimising the port call process.

1.5 Relation to other projects and initiatives

This work incorporates definitions and interpretations of terms from the ITPCO (2022), the IMO (2020), the Baltic and International Maritime Council (BIMCO) (2024) and the contractual documents referred to in the Grant Agreement No. 101138478 with Annexes and in the

DYNAPORT Consortium Agreement, unless explicitly stated otherwise, and have the same meaning.

Furthermore, there is a relation to the sister project MISSION, which is funded by the European Commission under the same call for proposals, *HORIZON-CL5-2023-D5-01*. For both projects, it is important to have a general process and actor model for ports and port call processes. This is crucial for understanding optimisation potentials and obstacles, as well as for building a good Information Communications Technology (ICT) infrastructure.

1.6 Relationship with other deliverables

For the development of a blueprint for optimising the port call process in *D2.2*, the results obtained in *D2.1* have been used. These results form the basis for the further development and refinement of the to-be port call process, whereby in particular the identified key factors and recommendations for improvement in *D2.1* have been considered in order to ensure efficient and sustainable optimisation.

Beyond that, the identified contractual and organisational obstacles as well as the creation of the necessary conditions for operational efficiency and JIT arrivals in the context of *D3.1* represent a decisive contribution to the development of the to-be process of the port call in the context of *D2.2*.

The terms and definitions used are based on the document *Common Terms and Definitions* by Voorspuij et al. (2025), which serves as a complementary reference and is continuously updated.

The *Maritime ICT Reference Architecture* (MIRA) document by Rødseth et al. (2025) provides a conceptually grounded reference framework for the standardisation and digitalisation of maritime information and communication processes in the context of port calls and ship operations. It also offers essential technical foundations that inform the development of the blueprint produced within the project. The current version of the MIRA document forms the basis for the forthcoming ISO 26166 standard and represents a preliminary version that will be further refined and elaborated as the standardisation work progresses. The latest state of the MIRA document is presented in Deliverable *D5.1*, Annex A.

2 Theoretical background

The coordination of port calls (the arrival and departure of a ship at a specific port as part of its journey or route; a ship may call at one or more berths during a single port call) is a highly complex, multi-layered process that requires close coordination and effective communication between many actors from different areas. A structured conceptual framework is needed to systematically record and analyse these interactions. Such a framework forms the methodological basis for the development of a targeted and implementable coordination concept that addresses existing challenges and offers practical solutions.

The central starting point for the development of such a concept is the precise definition of the requirements that the plan must meet. This is achieved by defining a clear purpose and realistic and verifiable objectives that consider a variety of technical, organisational and regulatory conditions. The integration of the perspectives and requirements of the stakeholders involved, such as port authorities, shipping companies, terminal operators and nautical services, is essential to develop a viable and accepted concept. In the context of the DYNAPORT project, this goal is specified in terms of increasing energy and process efficiency by establishing JIT arrival of ships, which is to be made possible by improved, data-supported coordination. At the same time, the aim is to maintain the operational independence of ports and the freedom of action of maritime trade.

The first step in this improved coordination is the exchange of information between the ship and the port. The ship is sending a request to the port, an ETA. On the ship's side, this requires, in particular, the timely transmission of a binding Requested Time of Arrival (RTA) by the port, which makes it possible to plan and optimise the ship's route in such a way that it is both resource-efficient and coordinated with the availability of port resources in terms of time. This targeted journey optimisation not only contributes to reducing emissions, but also helps to avoid unnecessary waiting times and bottlenecks in port operations.

The first step in this enhanced coordination is the exchange of information between the ship and the port. The ship submits an ETA, while the port provides a binding Requested Time of Arrival (RTA). This allows operations to be planned and aligned more effectively, enabling efficient use of available resources. Such early and reliable communication facilitates the proactive management of arrival and departure processes, minimising unnecessary waiting times and enhancing overall port efficiency. Moreover, it provides a foundation for further optimisation measures, such as dynamic schedule adjustments or ship prioritisation, thereby delivering both environmental and operational benefits.

To provide ships with a reliable RTA, forward-looking and continuously updated port planning is required. This includes recording and processing the ETA and detailed knowledge of planned ship operations. On this basis, the various port processes are coordinated, involving relevant stakeholders such as port and terminal planners, nautical services, operating companies and, where applicable, external service providers. These processes must not only be coordinated with each other, but also continuously monitored and adjusted as necessary, and communicated to all parties involved in an appropriate form. Transparent and responsive information sharing is of central importance here to be able to react flexibly to short-term changes in plans. Current, there are many different practices for send the RTA; some ports confirm as soon as possible after

receiving an ETA, while others send it, for example, when the ship is 40 nautical miles from the port.

The resulting improved coordination can be divided into two categories of exchange processes: Firstly, temporal coordination, which includes all relevant time data and, secondly, procedural coordination, in which information on terminals to be called at, cargoes to be handled, requirements for nautical assistance services, bunkering operations, maintenance measures and other logistical details must be systematically exchanged and coordinated.

Given this high level of complexity, it makes sense to divide the solution into clearly defined technical and organisational dimensions. Such a modular approach allows the complex interdependencies to be broken down into manageable functional units. This systematisation forms the basis for the layering of solution elements described in the following chapter, which facilitates step-by-step implementation in different port contexts.

In addition to technical feasibility, it is also essential to take external framework conditions into account when developing the concept. These include applicable legal regulations, international standards, technical standards and contractual obligations, which have a significant influence on the practical feasibility and design of the concept. In addition, it is necessary to integrate current developments in maritime logistics, regulatory changes and technological innovations into the planning in order to ensure a future-proof concept.

Another key success factor for the implementation of the desired optimisation measures is the approval of the stakeholders involved. Only if the planned changes are in line with the interests and expectations of the relevant actors can the necessary process adjustments be successfully implemented. To promote this approval, the DYNAPORT project relies on the use of demonstrators. These serve to test the proposed improvements under realistic conditions, systematically evaluate their impact and transparently demonstrate the added value of the measures from different perspectives.

Finally, it must be ensured that the solutions developed not only have an impact at the project level but can also be transferred to everyday industrial practice. This includes targeting relevant user groups, collaborating with standard-setting institutions and authorities, and involving the general public. The project's planned dissemination and communication measures make a key contribution to this by increasing the visibility of the project results, promoting knowledge transfer and providing impetus for broader implementation in the maritime industry.

2.1 Definition of the blueprint

In general, the term *blueprint* refers to a structured and standardised model or template that serves as a starting point for designing and optimising processes. A blueprint is a detailed and systematic representation of best practices, procedures and processes that can be used as a guide for developing and implementing efficient solutions. It is a kind of reference model that encompasses the essential elements and requirements of a process or system and serves as a basis for further development and improvement.

The blueprint is not just an abstract conceptualisation, but a concrete, implementable representation that integrates all relevant components of a process, from planning to execution. It is intended to provide a clear structure and a binding framework that links different actors or stakeholders and facilitates cooperation and communication. The aim of a blueprint is to provide

a flexible and adaptable template that allows specific needs and requirements of different environments or contexts to be considered, while at the same time ensuring a high level of efficiency and interoperability.

Within the DYNAPORT project, a blueprint is defined as a structured and standardised framework that provides an optimised basic structure for port call processes and thus serves as a starting point for the optimisation and standardisation of port call processes that uses an interaction-based approach between involved stakeholders. It covers all relevant components of a port call, from planning and execution to follow-up, and forms an integral framework that connects various actors and stakeholders. Similarly, the concept comprehensively addresses the current challenges facing ports worldwide, such as a lack of standardisation of processes and procedures, which lead to inefficiencies and increased costs, as well as communication deficits between the various actors in port operations, such as shipping companies, terminal operators, customs authorities and other stakeholders. These deficits often lead to delays, unused resources and, ultimately, reduced competitiveness for the ports concerned.

The purpose of the blueprint is to create a universally applicable solution that not only addresses the challenges mentioned above but also forms the basis for long-term improvement of port call processes. This solution is to be designed to be flexible enough to be adapted to different port contexts and regional characteristics. The blueprint considers both the infrastructural conditions and the specific operational and economic conditions of individual ports.

A key objective of the blueprint is to increase the efficiency of port calls by providing a clear, standardised and interoperable structure that promotes seamless cooperation between the various stakeholders. In addition, the sustainability of the processes is considered, particularly regarding the reduction of CO₂ emissions and the optimisation of resource use. The blueprint goes beyond a purely technical perspective to include organisational, contractual and communicative aspects that are crucial for the smooth running of port calls.

The blueprint thus represents an instance of a reference model that systematically sets out the necessary elements and processes for the effective and efficient execution of port calls. It contains the essential features, requirements and processes that serve as a basis for the development and implementation of solutions to improve port operations. The result is a modular and adaptable template that makes it possible to consider the different needs and characteristics of individual ports while achieving a high degree of interoperability and standardisation.

2.2 The port call process

Port calls are a central process in maritime transport, ensuring the safe, efficient and legally compliant handling of all port activities for a ship. They include essential procedures such as loading and unloading, passenger handling, bunkering and technical maintenance. At the same time, official inspections and administrative procedures are carried out to ensure compliance with national and international regulations. Through coordinated communication between the ship, port authorities and service providers, port calls contribute significantly to the optimisation of port logistics and the stability of global supply chains.

As an integral part of maritime transport chains, port calls consist of a multitude of coordinated processes involving different actors. This chapter provides a structured overview of the process aspects and stakeholders that are of central importance to the DYNAPORT project for the

development of a blueprint for a port call process, providing a comprehensive reference model for optimisation and standardisation. The selection of the processes described is specifically geared to the requirements of this model. Other existing definitions and alternative descriptive approaches have been deliberately excluded in order to focus on a clearly defined and specific basis.

The following sections are devoted to defining and describing the individual process components and the respective roles of the stakeholders involved. This creates a common understanding of the processes, which serves as a basis for further understanding of the chapter and enables the systematic recording and structuring of the port call process.

2.2.1 Port call – process steps

The visit of a ship has been divided into five logical phases within the framework of the developed blueprint and is based on the process steps outlined by Lind et al. (2019, p. 30). Each phase is characterised by clearly defined time limits and characteristic movement and communication sequences. These phases are described in detail below, linking the precise definition of their scope with a detailed explanation of the key tasks, actors and contexts.

— **Pre-arrival:**

The pre-arrival phase begins with the formal notification of the port call and concludes once the ship has reached the designated waiting area of the port. This phase encompasses all navigational actions and communication processes between the initial port call announcement and the ship's transition into the port area.

During the sea passage, ships provide updated estimated times of arrival, refine nautical documentation, and coordinate berth-related resources such as pilotage and towage. In parallel, safety and environmental procedures are prepared, customs and import processes are initiated, and terminal capacity is aligned with anticipated operations. Early and reliable information enables targeted eco-steaming, thereby reducing fuel consumption and mitigating subsequent waiting time.

As the ship approaches the port, it enters the Port Passage Planning Area (PPA) (a designated segment of the sea passage established by the port authority). Within this zone, a ship may already be treated as an Arrived Ship for the purpose of tendering the Notice of Readiness, even while still underway. Although the PPA may lie outside the legal, fiscal, or administrative boundaries of the port, it provides a controlled environment in which ships can adjust their speed optimally without jeopardising their allocated position within the port's passage or berth planning framework. The PPA thus functions as an upstream coordination space that prepares ships for orderly integration into subsequent port processes.

Following the PPA, the ship proceeds to the waiting area, where it formally attains Arrived Ship status for tendering the Notice of Readiness if this has not already occurred. This area, also defined by the relevant port authority, serves as the immediate holding zone for ships awaiting their turn in the operational sequence. It may likewise be located outside the strict administrative limits of the port, but its role within the arrival chain is clearly defined: to receive ships that have passed through the PPA and are now ready for controlled entry into the port area.

The port area, as understood in the DYNAPORT project, comprises all land and water spaces used for operational port activities, including approaches, anchorages, berths, yards and storage facilities (cf. IMO 1973). In this coordinated structure, the PPA and the waiting area form successive, interlinked stages, ensuring that ships transition smoothly from the broader sea passage into the operational heart of the port, thereby strengthening predictability, reducing congestion and improving the efficiency of port call processes.

— **Port arrival:**

The port arrival phase begins with the *End of Sea Passage* (EOSP) and includes the ship's entry into the waiting area of the respective port. EOSP refers to the moment when a ship completes the main ocean-going part of the voyage and transitions to port approach, pilot boarding, or coastal navigation. Following EOSP, the ship proceeds through the port-passage, which constitutes the navigational segment within the port environment. This passage encompasses the transit between the waiting area and the assigned berth, as well as potential intra-port passages, such as movements from one berth to another. It serves as the operational link between arrival at the port's approaches and the initiation of berthing procedures, integrating traffic management, nautical services, and port-specific navigational constraints.

The phase ends with the *'first line secured'* (the first securing of the mooring lines at the berth). If berths are equipped with automated mooring systems, it would be the first pad which is secured to the ship. During this period, all nautical movements and associated communication processes are carried out to ensure the transition from maritime transport to port infrastructure.

This phase is characterised by intensive coordination with, for example, vessel traffic services (VTS). In addition, other service providers provide support during the berthing process. The final allocation of the berth is also part of this process. In addition, safety-related checks are carried out in parallel, in particular regarding compliance with dangerous goods regulations and environmental legislation.

— **Berth visit:**

The berth visit phase begins at the moment the first line is secured, marking the initial attachment of the ship to the berth. It continues until the ship is fully moored, with all mooring lines properly tensioned from the ship and fastened to appropriate shore-based mooring facilities such as bollards, dolphins or comparable equipment. It ends with the release of the last line (*'last line released'*) as part of the departure maneuver. During this phase, all movements and communication processes related to cargo handling, passenger operations, and ship services take place.

— **Port departure:**

The departure phase starts when the ship has finished leaving its berth and ends once it has fully exited the port area. This phase covers all movements and communication activities from leaving the port up to the handover to the planning processes for the next port call. It includes navigating through the port passage, moving through any waiting areas, and reaching *Full Away on Passage* (FAOP), which is the point when the ship officially enters the sea passage. Key elements of this phase include nautical support from pilots and tugs, as well as the final clearance from the relevant port and traffic authorities.

— **Post-departure:**

The post-departure phase begins immediately with the transition to the actual sea voyage (on sea passage). During this phase, the ship proceeds continuously towards its next destination port, with all navigational and operational activities focused on the safe and

efficient execution of the voyage. Conceptually, the post-departure phase is closely linked to the subsequent pre-arrival phase, which covers the transition from the open-sea voyage to the preparatory measures for port entry. Due to these substantive overlaps, the two phases are not strictly delineated within the blueprint. The post-departure phase is considered to end with the initiation of the first preparatory activities for the port call. Nevertheless, it is revisited in this context to ensure a comprehensive understanding of the overall processes involved in port approach and maritime transport.

2.2.2 Port call – stakeholders

A port call is a highly complex, time-critical and interdisciplinary process in which numerous actors interact closely with each other. Each of these stakeholders plays a specific role, contributes different requirements, perspectives and responsibilities, and thus directly influences the efficiency, safety and sustainability of the overall process. In an increasingly digitalised and networked maritime environment, a common understanding among the groups of actors involved is of central importance, especially when it comes to developing and successfully implementing overarching concepts such as coordinated (JIT) arrivals.

As part of the DYNAPORT project, the blueprint developed for optimising port call processes was used to make a targeted selection of those stakeholders who are directly relevant for mapping and analysing the process chain. The following presentation follows this system and focuses exclusively on those actors who are explicitly considered in the blueprint. Other potentially involved actors are deliberately excluded, as they are only of secondary or indirect importance for process modelling within the scope of this blueprint.

The presentation includes both a definitional classification and a classification of the respective roles in the context of port calls. It thus serves as the basis for a common, process-oriented understanding and ensures that the analysis remains focused on the stakeholders actually depicted in the blueprint and relevant for process optimisation. An overview of the stakeholders considered in the blueprint is provided in Figure 1.

Additional stakeholders beyond the groups considered in the developed blueprint are listed in supplementary documents, such as the document *Common Terms and Definitions* (cf. Voorspuij 2025) and the document *FAL.5/Circ.52* (cf. IMO 2023), and can be used for further analysis and differentiation if necessary.

— **Ship Representative:**

The ship representative encompasses all relevant parties responsible for communication, organisation and operational procedures on the ship's side. This includes the following stakeholders in particular.

Shipping line:

The shipping line is usually the company responsible for operating the ship, either as the owner or as the charterer. Its tasks include determining the route, schedule and operational parameters.

Ship agent:

The ship agent acts as the representative of the ship operator on site and coordinates between the ship and shore-based institutions. Their tasks include registering the ship, arranging necessary services, handling documentation requirements and communicating with port authorities and terminal operators. Due to their central role in operational handling, ship agents are essential intermediaries between the interests of the ship and the requirements of the port.

Authorised representative:

The Authorised Representative is a person or organisation authorised by the shipowner or operator to coordinate all legal, contractual and administrative matters relating to the port call and to represent the shipowner or operator in dealings with third parties.

— **Nautical service provider (NSP)**

NSPs in ports are essential components of maritime infrastructure and ensure the safe, orderly and efficient handling of ship traffic within the port area. It is a party that provides nautical services to the ship. Key stakeholders in the context of the blueprint are:

Pilotage services:

Pilots take on the responsible task of navigating ships safely through the port area. Due to their local knowledge and legally prescribed activities, they are essential for safe approach and entry into the port. Their availability must be planned in advance, and they are an important part of arrival and departure coordination.

Towage services:

Tugboats assist ships in docking and undocking, especially ships restricted in their ability to manoeuvre. They are coordinated in close consultation with the captain, the agent and the terminal. The timely commissioning and availability of tugboats is crucial for the smooth running of port calls.

Mooring services (Linesmen):

Mooring lines ensure that the ship is securely moored at its berth. They are typically integrated into the operational arrival process and must be planned and coordinated in advance.

— **Maritime single window (MSW):**

The MSW refers to a central digital platform through which maritime and port-related administrative processes are coordinated. These include arrival and departure notifications, safety-related information, details of port calls and other related data that are exchanged nationally between the parties involved in a port call process. An effective MSW should be understood as a technology-neutral and trustworthy cooperation platform that enables the secure exchange of regulatory, operational and nautical information between public and private actors. (cf. IMO 2024)

— **Cargo services provider (CSP):**

CSPs cover all services related to a ship's cargo and freight. Cargo services include various specialised services that can vary depending on the type of freight, the requirements of the means of transport and local conditions. The basic tasks include the professional loading and unloading of goods, the provision of suitable handling equipment and qualified operating personnel.

In addition, the (interim) storage of cargo within the port area, the complete documentation of transport processes, and the management and monitoring of freight stocks are also essential components of this service area.

— **Ship service provider (SSP):**

SSP refers to all services related to the operation and maintenance of ships. These services can vary depending on the port location, ship type and individual requirements of the shipping company or operator.

The range of services typically covers four key areas: technical and operational services (e.g., maintenance, port assistance, loading and unloading), supply services (such as the provision of fuel, water or provisions), administrative and legally required services (such as customs clearance, inspections or certifications) and support measures for the crew working on board (e.g., crew changes, medical care or accommodation).

— **Authority:**

The party that receives information related to the port call, provides clearance to the ship's arrival and departure. For example, but not limited to: harbour master, customs, immigration, port health, port VTS, coastguard.

— **All relevant parties to the operations:**

This term is used in this deliverable to collectively denote all actors involved in port calls and related ship operations. It encompasses all entities participating directly or indirectly in the planning, coordination, execution, or monitoring of maritime activities (port side). This includes all organisations, authorities, service providers, berth planners, port planners and representatives whose engagement is essential to ensure the proper and efficient conduct of the respective operations.

Figure 1 Stakeholders involved in the proposed blueprint

The stakeholders described above form the backbone of the port call process. They are both the drivers and users of the coordination measures and information systems required for modern, efficient and sustainable port operations. A common understanding of these roles and interactions is a basic prerequisite for the development of standardised interfaces, legal frameworks and digitally supported tools that not only enable JIT coordination technically but also secure it organisationally and economically.

2.2.3 Port call – time stamps

In the context of modern port logistics and shipping optimisation, the precise recording, coordination and communication of temporal processes plays a central role. The ITPCO and the Global Maritime Energy Efficiency Partnerships Project (GloMEEP Project), a joint initiative of the Global Environment Facility (GEF), the United Nations Development Programme (UNDP) and the IMO, have presented, among other things, a systematic structuring of the port call process based on the use of standardised time stamps (cf. ITPCO 2022; GEF-UNDP-IMO GloMEEP Project and the Global Industry Alliance (GIA) 2020). These time stamps form the basis for transparent, predictable and resource-efficient port calls. They enable all stakeholders, from shipping companies to terminal operators and port authorities, to make time-critical decisions in a coordinated manner (cf. ITPCO 2022; GEF-UNDP-IMO GloMEEP Project and the GIA 2020). The individual time stamps are described in detail below in order to clearly illustrate their respective functions and significance in the context of the port call process. Building on this, the modified approach developed as part of this project is explained and justified. It is based on practical findings and concrete observations gained during the analysis in Deliverable *D2.1*. A brief overview of the key findings from *D2.1* can be found in Chapter 3.

ETA, RTA, Planned Time of Arrival (PTA), Actual Time of Arrival (ATA) – berth:

At the beginning of the port call process, the focus is on the ship's arrival at its assigned berth. The berth is the final destination in the port call chain and is the position within the terminal where the ship physically docks and where the actual port services as well as supply and service processes, take place. Due to its direct connection to terminal-internal resources, infrastructural availability and commercial scheduling decisions, the berth is of central

economic relevance. It is not only the spatial end point of the approach, but also the temporal pacemaker for subsequent ship movements and resource deployment.

— ETA – berth:

The estimated time at which the ship will reach its intended berth. This estimate is usually based on the ship's current position, speed and course, as well as external factors such as weather or traffic conditions in the port.

— RTA – berth:

This is the arrival time at the berth requested by the port and determined on the basis of information provided by the shipping company or the ship. It is used to coordinate the port call so that the arrival can be optimally coordinated with the availability of port resources, such as the terminal.

— PTA – berth:

The PTA represents the coordinated planning time agreed between all relevant parties at which the ship is to reach the berth. It is based on the RTA, considering operational possibilities and restrictions.

— ATA – berth:

The actual time at which the ship reaches its berth and the manoeuvre is completed.

ETA, RTA, PTA, ATA – Pilot boarding place (PBP):

An essential element of the port call is the transfer of command to a local pilot, who navigates the ship safely through the port area. This transfer takes place at a defined point at sea, known as the PBP. The PBP is a predefined geographical position in the port area where the pilot boards the arriving ship. This position is chosen so that a safe handover can be guaranteed, considering sea conditions, ship size and nautical features of the area.

— ETA – PBP:

The estimated time at which the ship will reach the PBP. This information is communicated to the port authorities and pilotage organisations to ensure that pilots are available in good time. Within the scope of the proposed blueprint, this time stamp is not considered, as explained above.

— RTA – PBP:

The port's preferred time for having the ship reaching the PBP, based on the ETA berth provided, the planned itinerary and operational requirements at the port.

— PTA – PBP:

The planned time agreed between the port side and ship side at which the ship is to reach the PBP.

— ATA – PBP:

The actual documented time at which the ship reaches the boarding point and the pilot comes on board.

Estimated Time of Start (ETS), Requested Time of Start (RTS), Planned Time of Start (PTS), Actual Time of Start (ATS) – Start of the services:

As soon as the ship is moored at its berth, a series of logistical services begins – e.g., container handling, tank operations or passenger changes. Their timing begins with the start time.

— ETS:

The predicted start time for a specific service, based on experience, internal planning and dependencies on other processes.

— RTS:

The start time of a service requested by the ship representative based on the ETS.

— PTS:

The planned start time of a service based on the transmitted RTS by the ship representative, which serves as an operational benchmark for staff and the resources deployed.

— ATS:

The actual documented time at which the specified service commenced (e.g., the first lifting of a container or the opening of a valve).

Estimated Time of Completion (ETC), Requested Time of Completion (RTC), Planned Time of Completion (PTC), Actual Time of Completion (ATC) – Completion of the services:

The completion of a service marks another milestone in the port call process and is crucial for subsequent activities, such as the ship's departure.

— ETC:

The estimated time at which a service will be completed. It is usually calculated based on the remaining quantity or duration of work.

— RTC:

The target time for the completion of a service, defined by the ship's representative, in order to ensure follow-up processes.

— PTC:

The agreed planned date for completion, which is derived from the deployment planning of personnel and equipment.

— ATC:

The actual measured time at which the service was fully completed, e.g., last container loaded, last tonne bunkered.

ETD (Estimated Time of Departure), Requested Time of Departure (RTD), Planned Time of Departure (PTD), Actual Time of Departure (ATD) – berth:

The departure from the berth is a critical point in the process, as it not only marks the end of port operations, but also has an impact on the rest of the itinerary and port logistics.

— ETD – Berth:

The estimated time at which the ship will leave its berth, based on the completion of all services and the availability of nautical assistance.

— RTD – Berth:

The desired time of departure of the ship.

— PTD – Berth:

The scheduled time set by the port, which serves as the basis for the organisation of all supporting services.

— ATD – Berth:

The actual time at which the ship leaves its berth, thereby opening up new berthing slots for subsequent ships.

The precise definition and application of standardised time stamps enable a comprehensive standardisation, digitalisation and optimisation of the port call process with regard to efficiency, environmental sustainability and predictability. The consistent use of these time stamps facilitates the coordinated arrival of ships, whether in the context JIT arrivals, synchronised approaches of multiple ships or other operational scenarios.

Such coordination supports the reduction of waiting times at anchor, allows for more efficient allocation of port resources and helps to avoid bottlenecks both at sea and on land. It enhances transparency among all stakeholders across the maritime transport chain and provides a foundation for anticipatory and sustainable port logistics.

In this respect, the GloMEEP project, a joint initiative of the GEF, the UNDP and the IMO, highlights four predefined time stamps that are considered particularly critical for the effective management of port calls (cf. GEF-UNDP-IMO GloMEEP Project and the GIA 2020). These time stamps are closely linked, causally interdependent and highly relevant in operational terms for the implementation of JIT arrival (see Figure 2). These include the ETC, ETD, RTD and RTA time stamps.

The concept described in the GloMEEP project particularly emphasises the PBP and the berth as central reference points for the temporal and operational control of port calls. These two key positions not only serve as geographical fixed points, but are also considered in the existing literature to be fundamental anchors for fine control, capacity planning and the efficient use of maritime infrastructure. Their particular significance stems from their dual function as operational control points and planning reference values within an increasingly data-driven system.

Figure 2 Key time stamps for a port call according to the GloMEEP project

A central component of this approach is the consideration of four time stamps, which are understood not as isolated planning variables, but as closely interlinked elements of a dynamic and causally dependent process. The arrival planning of a ship is therefore based primarily on the expected departure time from the currently occupied berth, which in turn is influenced by terminal and bunker-related services, weather conditions and the availability of nautical services. On this basis, a port authority calculates a realistic departure time, which in turn determines the earliest possible arrival time of the next ship at the PBP.

Within this process chain, the time stamps perform an operational control function. Their accuracy and timeliness have a direct impact on the quality of subsequent planning decisions. Delays or incorrect information in one link of the chain can have a cumulative effect on subsequent ships and significantly impair their operational efficiency. In this context, the RTA at the PBP in particular is considered the last active intervention point for the ship at sea: if this value is known and reliable, the ship can adjust its speed, save resources and reduce emissions. Missing or inaccurate data, on the other hand, often leads to inefficient behavior patterns such as ‘hurry up and wait’, which has both economic and environmental disadvantages.

In theory, this integrated approach opens the possibility of precise coordinated arrival of ships through standardised, systematically linked time stamps and cross-company coordination. It thus creates the basis for transparent, reliable and resource-efficient port calls with positive effects on decarbonisation, efficiency and the resilience of global supply chains.

However, implementing the control approaches developed in theory is proving challenging in practice. It has become apparent that the reliable and continuously updated transmission of these precise time data from the ship is associated with considerable difficulties. Determining the ETA and ETD for the berth or PBP requires accurate navigation data and regular updates, requirements that involve increased effort under real conditions at sea. In addition to the technical infrastructure, there is often a lack of institutional willingness to provide dynamic or sensitive operational data in a timely and reliable manner. Furthermore, there is often uncertainty regarding the responsibilities and obligations for transmitting this data, which leads to delays or ambiguities in communication. Delayed or incomplete feedback and conflicting data sources result in frequent coordination rounds, which further slowdown the process and impair its efficiency. These shortcomings make data-based control of ship arrivals considerably more difficult, especially regarding the precise planning of time slots and the early deployment of critical port resources.

To meet the challenges described above and at the same time increase both technical feasibility and willingness to cooperate on the part of the ships, the DYNAPORT project proposes an alternative, practice-oriented control approach. This approach deliberately adopts a simplified and user-oriented strategy by initially focusing on a single operational reference point, in this case the berth, as the basis for the arrival notice. The arrival notice refers to the communication sent to the notified party, providing information on the ETA of the shipment (cf. DCSA 2025). Within the framework of the DYNAPORT project, this definition is interpreted more broadly, considering not only the shipment but the entire ship. Rather than issuing notifications based on multiple geographically defined timestamp locations, the concept aims to streamline the spatial reference structure. The ETA and ETD information initially transmitted by the ship retains its central importance in the temporal coordination and prioritisation of ship arrivals. However, it is common practice for the ship to submit an ETA PBP. Based on this information, the port can subsequently derive the ETA at the berth, which then serves as the basis for determining both the RTA berth and the RTA PBP. Based on this initial time information, the process planning for the ship and port is carried out (see Figure 3): After receiving the ETA PBP and deriving the ETA berth, the port transmits specific and coordinated time information for the operational handover points, in particular in the form of:

1. RTA Berth / RTA PBP
2. PTA Berth / PTA PBP

3. ATA Berth / ATA PBP

This structure enables adaptive, resource-efficient and, at the same time, realistic control of port calls. It reduces the complexity at the beginning of the arrival notice on the ship side, while maintaining the precision required for port operations, and thus contributes to the harmonisation of theoretical control concepts with the practical requirements of dynamic, cooperative call management.

Figure 3 Simplified reference structure for ship-side arrival notice

The decision to initially require ships to report only an ETA berth, rather than also submitting an ETA PBP, is based on the principle of simplified handling and the need to foster greater willingness to participate in coordinated port call processes.

Especially in the early stages of implementation, it is crucial to keep data requirements for ships as minimal and manageable as possible. Many ship operators and crews are still reluctant to actively engage with new digital coordination systems, particularly when these introduce additional complexity, unfamiliar workflows, or increased reporting duties.

By focusing solely on ETA berth as the central time reference, the ship's crew is provided with a clear and intuitive target time, directly linked to the intended point of operation – the berth. There is no need to assess and transmit multiple time estimates for different process points, which may rely on different operational or technical assumptions.

This approach also supports a low-barrier entry into standardised, data-driven coordination, especially for ships without advanced ETA calculation systems or for smaller shipping companies with limited IT infrastructure.

Over time, the scope of reporting can be gradually expanded, e.g., by including ETA PBP, once standardised processes have been established, stakeholders have gained familiarity, and data quality can be assured. This step-by-step approach prioritises practicality and adoption over immediate comprehensiveness.

In summary, the exclusive use of ETA berth in the initial phase represents a pragmatic and user-oriented solution. It provides a sufficiently robust information base for port coordination without overburdening crews or operators, while laying the groundwork for a future expansion towards more precise and integrated time-based control.

The question of when time stamps such as ETA berth must be submitted is deliberately not standardised within the blueprint. In practice, the requirements for submitting such information can vary considerably depending on the organisational structures, level of digitalisation, berth allocation procedures, and involvement of different stakeholders within a port.

Some ports request the ETA berth several days in advance to enable early planning and coordination, while others require it only shortly before arrival due to more dynamic operational processes. Factors such as ship type, cargo category, or the overall traffic volume of a port can also influence the timing requirements.

Against this background, the blueprint consciously avoids rigid deadlines for submission. Instead, it adopts an open and flexible approach, allowing the concept to be adapted to local conditions. The aim is to provide a structured but non-restrictive framework that allows room for port-specific solutions.

This flexibility ensures that each port can define its own rules for submitting time stamps in accordance with its operational capacities and strategic objectives. Consequently, the blueprint establishes a foundation for tailored implementation that is both practical and compatible, especially in complex or less standardised environments.

Overall, the blueprint is not intended as a normative regulation but rather as a practical guide. It outlines methodological and structural principles for improved port call coordination while deliberately leaving space for local adaptation and gradual development.

Within the framework of the blueprint, the collection of additional time stamps for individual service providers is deliberately omitted to simplify handling for the users. The introduction and maintenance of individual time stamps for each separate service would significantly increase the complexity of the overall system and thereby hinder both acceptance and practical implementation. Instead, the various services, such as those provided by ship service providers or cargo service providers, are considered collectively at the berth. This means that their timing is not recorded separately but consolidated within common time stamps (start of the service/completion of the services). This consolidation allows for clearer and more efficient coordination without sacrificing the necessary level of detail in operational processes.

This deliberate limitation to a few centrally coordinated time stamps helps to keep the coordination process streamlined, promotes clear assignment of responsibilities, and at the same time realistically reflects operational practice. It thus represents a pragmatic compromise between the required process representation and practical feasibility, which is intended to increase the willingness to adopt the system among all participants. A detailed representation of the timestamp exchange as carried out in the proposed blueprint can be found in Figure 4.

Figure 4 Exchange of the time stamps

2.2.4 Port call – communication between the stakeholders

The safe and efficient handling of a port call is based largely on coordinated communication between the parties involved. This includes both traditional and digitalised information channels and requires a high degree of coordination, transparency and standardisation.

2.2.4.1 *Traditional means of communication*

A traditional means of communication that is still widely used in the maritime sector is Very High Frequency (VHF) radio. It is used for short-term, direct coordination between ship's command, pilots, VTS and operational port service providers such as tugs or mooring crews. Due to its immediate availability and widespread international use, VHF radio is considered a reliable means of real-time communication. However, it is limited in terms of structured data transmission, automated processing and documentation, which makes it only partially suitable for modern, digitised coordination processes.

2.2.4.2 *Electronic data platforms Communication platforms*

Alongside traditional radio communications, digital communication channels are becoming increasingly important. Structured data is exchanged via electronic platforms such as the MSW. These platforms support the digital transmission of arrival, cargo and safety information, which speeds up processes and reduces redundancies. The use of the MSW is mandatory under international regulations such as the IMO's Facilitation (FAL) Convention (cf. IMO 2024). The aim is to harmonise and simplify administrative processes, by avoiding redundant reports to different authorities.

2.2.4.3 *Standardised interfaces and system integration*

Cross-system communication during port calls requires technical and semantic standards that enable different IT systems to interpret and process information in a uniform manner. The aim is to exchange relevant data, such as arrival times, resource requirements or status changes, in a standardised, structured and, as far as possible, automated manner between shipping companies, port authorities, terminals and service providers.

These standardised interfaces form the basis for digitally supported, forward-looking coordination in the interests of more efficient port calls. They enable the development of shared situational awareness, reduce the need for manual coordination and promote the implementation of time-critical concepts such as JIT.

Nevertheless, the practical implementation of this systematic data integration has not yet been realised across the board. The status of implementation varies significantly between ports, countries and stakeholder groups. In many cases, there are still isolated solutions or processes involving media discontinuity, which limit the potential of digital port coordination.

The MIRA document of the DYNAPORT project comprehensively describes the underlying system requirements, communication flows and interface concepts. It serves as a reference framework for the development of the blueprint and supports the gradual development towards interoperable, standardised port call processes. (cf. Rødseth 2025)

2.2.4.4 *Other means of communication:*

In practice, the degree of digitisation depends heavily on the respective actors and their technical infrastructure. In many ports, email-based systems, web portals of port authorities or port

community systems (PCS) are still used in addition to standardised platforms. PCS serve as central platforms for the exchange of information between private and public actors in the port.

API (Application Programming Interfaces)-based applications and mobile applications are also increasingly being used, particularly for the integration of real-time data from sensors or AIS systems. These new technologies allow for greater integration of real-time information into operational decision-making processes.

2.2.5 Port call – contracts and agreements

The port call process of ships is embedded within a complex network of contractual and regulatory frameworks that structure the interactions between shipowners, charterers, port authorities, terminal operators and service providers. These legal and organisational provisions define the rights, obligations and liabilities of the actors involved and form the foundation for the lawful and efficient execution of maritime operations.

In commercial shipping, charter parties such as voyage and time charters constitute the central legal framework governing the employment of ships. Standardised contractual forms established by industry organisations set out the commercial relationships between shipowners and charterers, including provisions on laytime, demurrage and cargo handling obligations. In recent years these traditional frameworks have been supplemented by clauses that promote greater flexibility and environmental sustainability. Concepts such as JIT arrival and Virtual Arrival allow ships to adjust their speed to match port readiness, reducing waiting times, saving fuel and lowering emissions while maintaining contractual compliance. These developments illustrate a gradual shift from static contractual structures to performance-oriented agreements that link operational efficiency with environmental objectives.

Alongside charter parties, agreements governing terminal services and port operations play an important role. They define access to berths, cargo handling arrangements and the provision of ancillary services. Such contracts must comply with the principles of transparency, non-discrimination and accountability in order to ensure fair competition and predictable cost structures within the European port system.

The regulatory dimension of the port call process encompasses international, European and national instruments that address operational, safety and environmental requirements. At the European level, the European Maritime Single Window (EMSWe) environment harmonises reporting obligations prior to arrival and departure and enables the electronic transmission of standardised information. This transition from paper-based to digital reporting improves interoperability between stakeholders and supports more efficient coordination of port calls through enhanced data exchange and situational awareness.

International conventions such as the International Convention for the Prevention of Pollution from Ships (MARPOL), the International Convention for Safety of Life at Sea (SOLAS) and the International Safety Management (ISM) Code provide binding requirements for operational safety and environmental protection. These instruments set out obligations concerning waste management, fuel quality and risk control, forming a central part of the regulatory framework that governs port operations.

Recent regulatory developments, including the IMO's Carbon Intensity Indicator and the European Union Emissions Trading System, have begun to influence contractual practices.

Shipping agreements increasingly incorporate performance clauses and cost sharing mechanisms related to emissions compliance, demonstrating the growing integration of environmental regulation into commercial arrangements. This evolution reflects the emergence of a dynamic governance environment in which ecological performance and economic interests are closely connected.

At the national and local levels, port regulations and standard terms of service for pilotage, towage and mooring complement the international and regional frameworks. They establish the legal basis for the provision of mandatory services and ensure the safe and orderly conduct of ship traffic within specific port jurisdictions.

Taken together, these contractual and regulatory structures form a complex legal and operational ecosystem that governs the port call process. Contracts define the commercial relationships and responsibilities of maritime stakeholders, while regulations guarantee safety, environmental protection and transparency. Their interaction provides the foundation for a modern, sustainable and legally robust port environment that is increasingly shaped by digitalisation and the global objective of decarbonising maritime transport.

3 Current situation of the port call processes

This chapter highlights the current status of port call processes based on the key findings from the previously developed deliverable *D2.1*. It emphasises existing structures, communication channels and operational practices as currently applied in different port locations. In addition, a systematic comparison is made between current practice and the guidelines proposed by the IMO for harmonising operational communication and data exchange in the port arrival process (cf. IMO 2023). The aim is to clearly identify existing deviations and structural deficits. Finally, the chapter outlines the extent to which the concept of coordinated arrival of ships can offer a solution to address existing coordination problems and provide operational support for the implementation of international standards.

3.1 Summary of challenges identified in D2.1

This chapter revisits the previously identified challenges related to the as-is state of port call processes in order to provide a structured summary and a coherent overall picture. Furthermore, the obstacles associated with the implementation of JIT arrivals, identified through the literature review and the workshops attended, are outlined once again. The aim is to consolidate existing insights and offer a comprehensive overview of key issues and influencing factors.

Based on the research methods used, both cross-port and port-specific challenges were identified that affect different dimensions of port operations and infrastructure. These challenges include general problems that affect most ports, as well as specific difficulties that arise from the individual circumstances and needs of individual ports.

A key problem is the lack of harmonisation of processes and communication systems, which leads to delays and inefficient workflows. As a result, data cannot be exchanged seamlessly between the actors involved, resulting in inefficient process transitions between the various stakeholders. This particularly affects the handling of unforeseen disruptions or irregular occurrences, such as unpredictable weather conditions, unforeseeable waiting times, ship delays or unforeseen technical problems. These require a quick and coordinated response but are difficult to manage due to inadequate communication or unclear responsibilities. These findings are underlined by statements from the table-top session, in which both DYNAPORT and MISSION project partners participated. It was emphasised that the lack of communication between different stakeholders leads to inefficient workflows. It was also highlighted that it is not clearly communicated when and to whom information should be communicated, resulting in a lack of incentive to share information.

The insufficient use of modern digital technologies and information systems is identified as one of the main causes of the challenges mentioned. In some ports, logistical processes are still managed using outdated or inflexible systems. This particularly affects communication and data exchange between the various stakeholders, such as port operators, shipping companies, freight forwarders and customs authorities. The inadequate digital infrastructure and lack of willingness to share information leads to fragmented data, which makes it difficult to coordinate processes across multiple ports. Without a harmonised digital infrastructure, information gaps and delays often occur, which can destabilise the entire logistics chain.

Another significant problem concerns the lack of coordination between the various stakeholders involved in the port call processes, such as port operators, shipping companies, freight

forwarders and customs authorities. These stakeholders often have different, sometimes incompatible, objectives and priorities, which impedes effective collaboration and smooth port calls. For example, during the table-top session, it was noted that the lack of incentive to share data, due to unclear guidelines for data transmission, makes it difficult to calculate the exact ETA, as this is based on outdated or inaccurate information.

Furthermore, it has been found that the lack of standardisation in the handling of time stamps and processes leads to inconsistencies in the planning and execution of port calls, which in turn complicates coordination between ports and logistics partners. The discussion during the table-top session revealed significant deficits in the communication of time stamps. It was found that only the ETA is officially transmitted, while other relevant time stamps, such as the RTA or the PTA, are not used, known or communicated. In addition, the ETA provided is often described as outdated and inaccurate. Although ship operators and terminals have more precise ETA estimates, these are not widely shared. In this regard one key problem is the distinction between the 'serious' ETA, which the crew is aware of, and the 'administrative' ETA, which is often inaccurate. This discrepancy is due, among other things, to a lack of incentives to align the actual ETA with the administrative ETA, which significantly impairs planning and efficiency in port operations.

The results of the on-site studies and the table-top session show that the transmission of time stamps often does not take place within the intended time frame. These delays affect the timely flow of information, which in turn reduces the efficiency of operations. Furthermore, it limits the precision and accuracy of data processing, jeopardising the reliability of the entire process. Ports emphasised that under these circumstances, JIT arrivals of ships are not feasible. Instead, many ports follow a first-come-first-serve approach, which makes it much more difficult to implement a JIT approach.

Finally, the aspect of regulatory requirements was also highlighted as a significant challenge. Different regulations and legal frameworks that apply in different ports make it difficult to quickly adapt processes and impair the flexibility of the stakeholders involved. This particularly affects the handling of customs clearance, security precautions and environmental regulations, which are regulated individually in each port and thus lead to additional administrative burdens. During the table-top session, the Port of Gothenburg also pointed out the challenges associated with spot-market ships, whose contracts do not include specific clauses for JIT port calls. First and foremost, ships operated under a voyage charter often have contractual restrictions that affect their flexibility and efficiency. These regulations require bulk carriers and tankers to call at the next port as quickly as possible, regardless of whether a berth is actually available. This contractual obligation, which is based on the so-called 'due despatch' clause, aims to ensure that the voyage is completed as quickly as possible, but often results in inefficient port calls. Ships frequently experience waiting times at ports, which result in increased operational costs, elevated greenhouse gas emissions, and reduced capacity to implement strategies such as coordinated ship arrival or JIT arrival concepts. The relevance of this obstacle varies depending on the operating strategy, market conditions and the contractual modalities, which adds an additional layer of complexity to port planning.

The challenges mentioned above require a thorough and targeted examination of the standardisation and digitalisation of the relevant processes, not only to optimise the efficiency of port call processes in the long term and to enable JIT arrival, but also to ensure smooth and

coordinated cooperation between the various players in port operations. Closer cooperation between the stakeholders involved and the implementation of modern digital technologies can be essential approaches to overcoming these challenges. In view of the increasing complexity of port logistics and the large number of parties involved, it is crucial to standardise and automate processes using standardised procedures and digital technologies. Within this framework an incentive system needs to be introduced to increase the acceptance and reliability of time stamps in the port. Such a system should aim to motivate all stakeholders to provide accurate and up-to-date time stamps that are considered reputable and trustworthy. This could be done, for example, by linking compliance with time stamps to operational advantages or financial incentives. According to the results of the table-top session, it is also essential to adapt the contractual framework and close legal gaps so that clear guidelines and liabilities can be created for all parties involved. Improving coordination and communication in the maritime sector offers several significant advantages that can significantly enhance both the efficiency of port processes and the environmental performance of port calls. One major advantage is the reduction of energy consumption and emissions, on the route as well as in the port area, as ships are able to optimally control their speed and thus avoid unnecessary waiting times and the associated energy consumption. This results in a significant reduction in emissions, as fewer ships must be at anchor, which in turn improves air quality in the port area. Another important aspect is the improvement of navigational safety, as the reduction in the number of ships at anchor minimises the risk of incidents such as collisions or other safety issues. In addition, more precise planning and coordination of arrival times ensures that resources can be used more efficiently, making operations more reliable and predictable for both port operators and cargo owners. The improvement in operational predictability has the advantage for cargo owners that they can better coordinate their logistical operations and have greater planning certainty regarding the arrival times of their goods.

However, to fully realise these benefits, close cooperation between key stakeholders is required, including port operators, shipping companies, logistics companies and other players in the maritime supply chain. Only through coordinated action can the efficiency of the entire logistics process chain be increased. This joint effort not only leads to better utilisation of port capacities but also contributes to more sustainable and safer shipping.

3.2 Summary of deviations from the proposed IMO port call process

During the ongoing digitalisation and standardisation of the maritime supply chain, the IMO has proposed a framework for harmonising communication processes during port calls. This framework is set out in its document *FAL.5/Circ.52 – Guidelines for Harmonised Communication and Electronic Exchange of Operational Data for Port Calls*, which builds on the work carried out by the ITPCO. The aim of these guidelines is to establish globally accepted data formats, time stamp definitions and transmission processes to enable more efficient, interoperable and transparent port logistics. (cf. IMO 2023)

However, the reality in many ports still deviates significantly from this ideal scenario. In practice, there are a variety of challenges that hinder the consistent implementation of IMO requirements: technical incompatibilities, fragmented system landscapes, differing definitions and local routines mean that communication between ship management, shipping companies, port authorities and terminals is often inconsistent, error-prone and delayed.

A key concern of the IMO is the standardisation of time stamps, in particular ETA, RTA, PTA, ATA, ETD, RTD, PTD and ATD, each with a clear assignment to a defined reference position. This harmonisation is intended to create a reliable basis for digital port communication and comprehensive coordination between ship management, port authorities, terminals and other stakeholders. In practice, however, this form of standardisation is often not in place. In many cases, time stamps remain either outdated, incomplete or are not regularly maintained, which makes operational planning considerably more difficult and leads to a lack of transparency and inefficiencies along the process chain.

In addition, the IMO guidelines stipulate the introduction of an MSW, through which all relevant information about the ship and cargo is to be transmitted to the competent authorities in a single, digital format. In reality, however, this data is often transmitted redundantly by email, fax or via non-standardised platforms, leading to duplicate reports, manual rework and media breaks.

The underlying data model is clearly defined in the guidelines, with the IMO Compendium functioning as a conceptual model. It specifies the semantic and structural relationships of the relevant data elements but is not intended for direct technical implementation. Instead, it is mapped onto three established technical standards — the UNECE Core Component Library (MMT), the WCO Data Model, and ISO 28005 — all of which are central to the present project and are currently undergoing revision.

Although the Compendium thus provides a unified foundation for consistent and interoperable digital communication among all participating stakeholders, this conceptual framework is often only partially implemented in practice. Many ports, terminals, and service providers rely on proprietary IT systems tailored to their own operational logic, data structures, and processes. Standardised API-based connectivity is frequently lacking or insufficiently realised. This results in media-disruptive transitions, limited system-to-system compatibility, and significant challenges for cross-system process integration. Consequently, the efficiency of port coordination is constrained, and the consistent use of harmonised, machine-readable data formats, as envisaged by the IMO, remains limited. In addition, the IMO guidelines actively promote the concept of JIT arrival in order to avoid unnecessary waiting times, resource commitment and emissions. This principle requires precise, timely and reliable communication. In reality, however, generous time buffers continue to be used, as there is often a lack of confidence in reliable arrival times or the real-time availability of relevant information.

There are also differences in information security: The IMO requires the secure transmission and processing of sensitive operational data (cf. IMO 2021). In practice, however, it is not uncommon for unsecured channels such as email to be used to transmit ETA information or slot allocations – with the corresponding risk of errors or data loss.

In summary, it can be said that there is still considerable need for implementation in practice. The differences lie primarily in the lack of technical integration, the heterogeneous system landscape and the lack of standardisation of terms and processes. Consistent implementation of the IMO guidelines therefore offers great potential for increasing efficiency, particularly about JIT concepts and data-based port coordination.

This discrepancy between the standard and reality has been summarised in the Table 1.

Table 1 Comparison of IMO requirements with actual practice

Aspect	IMO-Guidelines	Practical Experience
Time stamps	Consistently defined, clearly assigned to the reference position.	Time stamps are often not communicated at all or only selectively, due to a lack of data maintenance and willingness to update.
Communication	Via a MSW, just once, digital	Multiple transmissions via different channels (email, fax, local systems).
Data model	Use of the IMO Compendium with standardised, API-supported interfaces	Individual IT systems without standardised APIs, lack of integration, manual data entry
System Environment	Networked, compatible, automated	Fragmented, isolated systems, often analogue or semi-automated processes
JIT arrival	Supports the reduction of waiting times and emissions	Conservative time buffers, little dynamic adjustment, first-come-first serve
Data security & integrity	Digital authentication, secure and traceable data transmission	Use of insecure channels (email, Excel), lack of validation and traceability

3.3 Potential solution for improvement: JIT arrival

The concept of JIT arrivals aims to guide ships so that they arrive in the port area at exactly the time when berths, fairways and nautical services are actually available. This avoids ships having to wait for hours or days in the roadstead outside the port – a classic inefficient and emission-intensive buffer that has been common in conventional planning models to date. (cf. GEF-UNDP-IMO GloMEEP Project and the GIA 2020)

Scientific studies confirm the effectiveness of JIT: A study commissioned by IMO-Norway GreenVoyage2050's GIA to Support Low Carbon Shipping, based on AIS data from 2019, found fuel and CO₂ reductions of an average of 14% per container voyage when speed was optimised over the entire duration of the voyage. Even when applying the JIT concept only in the last 24 hours, the savings were approximately 5.9%, and in the last 12 hours approximately 4.2%. (cf. Logistics Update Africa 2022) Further simulations in the Port of Rotterdam showed that JIT planning 12 hours before arrival already enables an average of 9% fuel savings. (cf. IMO 2020)

To achieve these effects, reliable, early and dynamic information flows are required, especially for time parameters such as ETA, PTA, RTA and ATA/ATD. Equally essential is the use of uniformly defined time stamps linked to a unique reference point, as well as the digital transmission of this data via interoperable interfaces. The Just-in-Time (JIT) arrival concept directly addresses these requirements by ensuring the continuous, precise and standardised provision of time-critical information. JIT arrival therefore directly fulfils the guidance and the associated conceptual data sets defined in the IMO guidelines and the IMO Compendium. (cf. GEF-UNDP-IMO GloMEEP Project and GIA 2020).

Furthermore, JIT can serve as an accelerator for the harmonisation of port communication. To successfully implement JIT, shipping companies, ports, terminals, pilots and other service providers must have access to a common, trustworthy and machine-readable database.

Overall, JIT arrival acts as a catalyst for internal organisational change and the establishment of a data-driven process culture. Through transparent coordination, structured communication, and automated data capture, collaboration among stakeholders is enhanced, information gaps are reduced, and the technical and organisational foundations for more resilient and environmentally friendly port call processes are established. At the same time, JIT arrival enables both ecological and economic efficiency gains while supporting the operational implementation of the key principles outlined in the IMO guidelines. By linking information flows, process coordination, and speed management, JIT provides a pragmatic approach to transforming port logistics towards a standardised, data-driven, and resource-efficient maritime transport chain.

4 Methodology

This study draws upon the Operational Viewpoint (OV) of the Unified Architecture Framework (UAF) as a conceptual reference model for analysing operational processes. The OV highlights the identification of activities and responsible actors, capturing tasks, information flows, and organisational relationships, while remaining independent of specific technical implementations. (cf. No Magic, Inc. 2025) In order to represent these operational elements in a structured and analysable manner, model-based approaches are particularly useful. In the context of business process analysis and design, a variety of notations are available, depending on the intended purpose and application domain. Freund and Rücker (2019) identify two widely recognised standards in this regard: The Business Process Model and Notation (BPMN) and the Decision Model and Notation (DMN). DMN primarily aims to model decision-making logic, i.e. to represent how decisions are made and which rules underlie these processes. (cf. Freund and Rücker 2019)

BPMN has established itself as a widely used standard in the analysis and design of processes, i.e. the temporal and logical sequence of activities, events and decisions within a business process. The strength of BPMN thus lies in describing ‘Who does what, when and in what order?’ As a graphical notation language, BPMN was developed with the aim of representing complex processes within and between organisations in a comprehensible, consistent and standardised manner. The method is not only used for the pure visualisation of process steps but also forms the basis for process analysis and the identification of weak points. A key advantage of BPMN is its accessibility for different target groups: both business and technical stakeholders can use the notation to develop a common understanding of process logic and its chronological sequence. BPMN is not limited to the internal process optimisation of individual organisations but is also suitable for representing inter-organisational processes in which several actors, systems and roles are interrelated. This is precisely where the method's particular potential lies: it enables a common understanding of processes, creates transparency regarding responsibilities and time references, and can serve as a basis for digitisation projects.

However, DMN is of secondary importance in the context of this deliverable, as the DYNAPORT project does not focus on modelling decision rules. Instead, the focus is on the structural description and coordination of a comprehensive target process with the aim of consistently recording and harmonising the port call process across different organisations and translating it into a common coordination logic. BPMN is significantly better suited to this form of procedural modelling, as it focuses on processes, role allocations and temporal dependencies.

Within the framework of the DYNAPORT project, BPMN is therefore used as a methodological tool to develop a comprehensive process model. The aim is to harmonise the previously fragmented and heterogeneous processes associated with the arrival, coordination and handling of seagoing ships and to map them in the form of a standardised target process. This model, developed with the help of BPMN, serves as a target vision for coordinated, digitally supported port call management. The target process derived from this not only represents a methodological basis for subsequent technical implementation, but also a central prerequisite for improved cooperation, transparency and predictability in the port ecosystem.

The comprehensive notation of BPMN allows complex processes, role distributions and temporal dependencies to be mapped. At the same time, however, this complexity poses a challenge:

BPMN diagrams can be difficult to understand for those involved who have no formal modelling experience due to their wealth of detail. Against this background, the process model to be developed will remain as low-threshold and intuitively accessible as possible, allowing all relevant actors to understand the processes and use the developed target process model as an effective basis for communication.

Against this background, a conscious decision was made to limit the modelling to the basic elements of BPMN. The full specification of BPMN, as presented in the system described by Freund and Rucker (2019), includes many object types and extension options that may be useful for very detailed or technical modelling, but would create unnecessary complexity for the objectives pursued here. For reasons of comprehensibility, readability and connectable communication, the project therefore uses a reduced selection of modelling elements that can map the core process clearly and comprehensibly.

Specifically, this means that the DYNAPORT project works exclusively with so-called flow objects (such as activities, events and gateways), connecting objects (such as sequence flows) and participants (pools and lanes to represent actor roles). On the other hand, advanced modelling elements such as artefacts, data objects, event types, specialised tasks, intermediate events or sub-processes in the broader sense are deliberately omitted. This decision not only serves to reduce technical complexity, but also promotes content connectivity among stakeholders who are primarily anchored in process practice rather than modelling methodology.

The BPMN elements used in the project are listed and described in more detail in Table 2 below to provide a clear understanding of the representation method used and to make the methodological approach comprehensible.

Table 2 BPMN elements

Symbol	Designation	Meaning
	Pools and lanes	Pools and lanes represent responsibilities for tasks. A pool or lane can be an organisation, a role or a system. A pool can have several lanes.
	Blank start event	The process starts.
	Blank end event	The process is finished.
	Task	A task is a work unit.
	Exclusive gateway	At a junction, the flow is directed to exactly one outgoing edge, depending on the junction conditions. During a join, it waits for one of the incoming edges to activate the outgoing flow.
	Parallel gateway	When the sequence flow branches, all outgoing edges are activated simultaneously. When joining, all incoming edges are waited for in order to activate the outgoing flow.
	Sequence flow	The sequence flow defines the order of execution.

5 Blueprint of port call processes

This chapter explores the development of a comprehensive blueprint designed to provide a structured foundation for the analysis and improvement of complex operational processes. The aim is to foster a shared understanding of key workflows and to highlight opportunities for standardisation and efficiency gains. The subchapter *Design of the blueprint* outlines the conceptual structure and methodological considerations underlying the creation of the model. Building on this, the subchapter *Blueprint of port call processes* illustrates how the blueprint can be applied to a specific context within maritime operations.

5.1 Design of the blueprint

Given the high level of complexity inherent in the port call process, which arises from the large number as well as the organisational and functional heterogeneity of the actors involved, a systematic decomposition of the solution into specific technical dimensions, hereinafter referred to as layers, appears to be a promising approach. Although these layers are not entirely decoupled from one another, their conceptual separation enables a structured analysis of the underlying challenges. At the same time, this layered approach provides the basis for a targeted and coordinated interaction between the various system components on both the ship and port sides. It should be emphasised that the blueprint primarily addresses the procedural sequence of the necessary steps within the port call process. The precise operational handling of individual tasks, including the specific modalities of communication between actors in day-to-day practice, is intentionally not addressed at this stage. These communicative and operational details are comprehensively covered in the MIRA document by Rødseth et al. (2025), which should be consulted where required to obtain a deeper understanding of the communication structures and interaction processes.

This methodological decomposition makes it possible to model complex interdependencies in a comprehensible manner, to transparently represent functional dependencies, and to assign technical and organisational measures in a purposeful way. In particular, with regard to improving the temporal and procedural coordination between sea-side and land-side operations, this approach offers a differentiated perspective that promises both greater planning accuracy and more efficient resource utilisation.

In addition to the layer structure, however, further supportive developments are required in selected key areas to ensure the intended functionality and effectiveness of the overall concept. These supporting elements, such as those concerning data infrastructure, legal frameworks, standardisation, or stakeholder integration, form the foundation for the successful implementation of the coordination solution in an operational context.

Figure 5 provides a schematic representation of the proposed layered architecture as well as the accompanying areas of development. While this chapter presents a detailed explanation of each layer and analyses their roles and relevance within the overall system, the subsequent sections focus more closely on the complementary developments necessary for the practical realisation and long-term establishment of the solution.

3 LAYERS APPROACH

Figure 5 Layers approach

5.1.1 Operations layer

This layer of the blueprint developed within the DYNAPORT project refers to the physical processes that take place both on board ships and within the port environment. Particular attention is given to ship movements and the use of technical equipment. The objective of this layer is to embed the proposed solution within the operational context of real-world port activities by analysing those processes that are triggered through coordination among the involved actors.

To develop this layer, detailed on-site observations were carried out at the project's partner ports. These enabled a differentiated analysis of typical process chains across various operational configurations. Since the blueprint is designed as a generic approach, intended to be applicable regardless of specific port structures and trading conditions, both commonalities and differences between the ports were considered in this layer. As such, it provides the foundation upon which the higher layers of the model can be built in a consistent and robust manner.

The findings of these investigations are documented in Deliverable D6.1, which provides a systematic definition of port call processes. This report outlines the sequence of physical activities carried out by the actors involved in a port call, identifies relevant interfaces and resources, and consolidates these elements into a structured system definition. In addition, the report includes schematic representations that support the analysis of the complex network of interacting processes among various stakeholders (cf. Braga et al. 2025).

In parallel to the analysis of physical processes, aspects of navigational safety were addressed in Deliverable D4.1. Based on literature reviews and consultations with expert groups, this report analyses key factors influencing maritime safety. The resulting insights have been incorporated into the foundational layer of the blueprint to ensure that safety-related requirements are considered from an early stage. Moreover, risk mitigation measures derived from these findings are integrated into the overall blueprint framework (cf. Schuett et al. 2024).

Based on the results of these two deliverables, the foundational layer has been formalised. It serves as a structured framework for organising operational processes and contributes to the systematic assessment and further development of their efficiency.

5.1.2 P3C layer

The second layer of the blueprint is dedicated to the coordination and communication among the involved stakeholders, with the objective of enabling coordinated ship arrivals. Currently, this communication is highly decentralised in most ports. The second layer of the framework addresses the coordination and communication among the actors involved, with the aim of enabling harmonised and temporally aligned ship arrivals. At present, communication in most ports is highly decentralised, resulting in a large number of bilateral coordination processes. Instead of clearly structured information flows, a variety of sometimes redundant exchanges evolve, for instance between the ship, represented by the agent, and different port stakeholders such as terminal operators or maritime service providers. This multitude of parallel interactions arises not least because several terminals within a single port coordinate their planning only to a limited extent and thus schedule the ships destined for their facilities largely independently of one another.

This fragmented communication and decision-making structure impedes the seamless synchronisation of port operations. As a consequence, potential efficiency gains remain unrealised, since delays, resource bottlenecks, or idle times can hardly be anticipated or jointly mitigated. Overall, it becomes evident that the core challenge lies less in the absence of technological capabilities than in the lack of overarching coordination between the terminal-specific planning entities.

To optimise this process, the blueprint proposes the introduction of a central coordination element, known as the P3C. The concept of the P3C is described, among others, in the JIT Arrival Guide and the PortCDM Report, and is based on the principle of central coordination of port call processes (cf. GEF-UNDP-IMO GloMEEP Project and the GIA 2020; Lind et al., 2019). At the core of the P3C lies the structured exchange of information between stakeholders, alongside the temporal coordination of their activities. Consequently, the P3C acts as an intermediary between ship-side and port-side operations (see Figure 6). It collects and disseminates relevant information, manages communication among stakeholders, and facilitates coordinated planning based on real-time data and synchronised time stamps. Thus, the P3C constitutes an organisational entity that synchronises processes and enhances operational efficiency.

P3C AS AN INTERFACE BETWEEN SHIP AND PORT

Figure 6 P3C as an interface

The P3C should not be understood as a specific IT system, but rather as a conceptual coordination approach. Depending on the port’s organisational structure, this role may be undertaken by different institutions. Its aim is to support the various processes involved in a port call and to facilitate cooperation among the participants. These include, for example, the coordination of berth and terminal resources, alongside various supporting measures aimed at improving the monitoring and management of ship movements, such as the use of location-based technologies and environmentally conscious operating practices.

Although the P3C plays a central role in the operational coordination of port calls, it is important to clearly distinguish it from the concept of the MSW. The MSW primarily functions as a regulatory and administrative interface through which ships submit standardised information electronically to the relevant authorities before, during, and after their port stay, as mandated by the IMO under the FAL Convention (cf. IMO 2024). The focus of the MSW thus lies on regulatory compliance and the simplification of formal procedures.

In contrast, the P3C is not designed for regulatory purposes but concentrates on the temporal and operational coordination of the involved actors. It enables proactive alignment and synchronisation of operational activities to achieve efficient process planning. While both systems can fundamentally interact and partially rely on the same data sets, they serve fundamentally different functions: the MSW answers the question ‘What needs to be reported?’, whereas the P3C addresses ‘How are operations coordinated in real time?’.

Consequently, the two concepts complement rather than replace each other. A clear functional distinction is essential to ensure that both regulatory requirements and operational optimisation potentials are effectively and purposefully fulfilled.

5.1.3 Contracts and regulations layer

The third layer within the DYNAPORT blueprint represents the governance and compliance dimension of the port call process. It illustrates how existing legal obligations, regulatory requirements, and contractual dependencies structure, guide, and adapt the course of a port call to operational developments. Central to this layer is the management-level flow of

information, which supports decision-making regarding planning, approval of actions, and validation of compliance throughout the ship's stay in port.

The aim of this layer is not to create new contracts or regulations but rather to model the flow of existing legal and contractual provisions throughout the port call process. It provides transparency regarding the timing of obligations, their interdependencies, and the operational measures they trigger. Changes in planning, such as delayed arrivals or disruptions in port services, can be documented and traced back to the corresponding obligations. This ensures that ports, shipping companies, and service providers can coordinate their actions effectively without violating existing agreements or regulatory requirements.

From a regulatory perspective, this layer encompasses international conventions of IMO, such as the FAL Convention, MARPOL, and SOLAS, European frameworks, notably Regulations (EU) 2017/352 on port services and (EU) 2019/1239 on the EMSWe, as well as national regulations and standards, for instance concerning pilotage and towage services. The blueprint does not list individual contracts or regulations by name. Rather, its focus is on representing the associated measures and procedures, including the preparation of contracts, the activation and execution of obligations, and the submission of mandatory notifications. This approach allows the entire operational course of a port call to be made comprehensible, accounting both for standard procedures and potential deviations. In doing so, the blueprint provides a transparent framework for systematically capturing and managing the interaction between legal requirements and operational processes.

Taken together, the contracts and regulations layer functions as the regulatory and legal backbone of the port call process. It ensures that the implementation of a synchronised, event-driven operational model, in which multiple actors exchange real-time data via the P3C, while complying fully with maritime law and established commercial practices. The primary objective of this layer is to present and harmonise existing legal frameworks in a logical sequence, thereby enabling coordinated port call operations to be executed reliably and systemically, without compromising the integrity of existing contractual relationships.

5.2 Blueprint of port call processes

The following subsection presents a structured analysis of the port call process by breaking it down into its individual phases. This approach aims to provide a comprehensive understanding of the complex interactions and operational dynamics that characterise the process. Each phase is examined separately to highlight its specific features, procedural requirements, and the roles of the stakeholders involved.

In parallel, the respective layers of the underlying blueprint are referenced throughout the analysis. By linking these layers to the individual phases of the port call, it is possible to illustrate which events occur simultaneously, how different processes interact, and where overlaps or interdependencies arise. In a subsequent subsection, various approaches and methods of the blueprint are addressed. The blueprint itself constitutes an integrated model of an idealised port call process, in which theoretical foundations and practical applications are closely interwoven. The approaches and methods embedded within the model function as methodological instruments, enabling the systematic translation of abstract conceptual insights into actionable measures. Through this reciprocal interplay of theory and practice, the model provides a coherent basis for the consistent and impact-oriented implementation of the port call process in real operational contexts.

More generally, the blueprint facilitates the implementation of an idealised port call process by providing a clearly structured and standardised framework for operational procedures. This framework offers guidance to all ports by transparently outlining process steps, role assignments, and information requirements, thereby supporting the consistent execution of port call activities. In particular, it enables smaller ports with limited resources to plan and coordinate operations efficiently without the need for extensive internal organisational structures. The blueprint serves as a guiding instrument, defining minimum standards, communication channels, and responsibilities. At the same time, it ensures that ports of different sizes can be seamlessly integrated into the overarching port call process, maintaining interoperability between smaller and larger, more formalised port facilities.

5.2.1 Pre-arrival

5.2.1.1 *Contracts and regulations layer*

The pre-arrival phase constitutes the initial stage of the overall port call process and thus represents the first formal point of interaction between the respective actors. During this phase, the foundations for both operational and administrative procedures are established. Its purpose is to initiate structured communication between the ship's representative and the relevant port-side stakeholders while simultaneously preparing, defining, and initiating the necessary commercial arrangements. At the same time, the pre-arrival phase cannot be regarded as a strictly delineated starting point, since communication and coordination activities often begin earlier. For example, the ship's representative, acting in the role of a ship agent, may already establish contact with the terminal of the next port during the ship's berth stay at the port of departure in order to submit a preliminary request for the upcoming port call and to exchange initial information required for operational planning. These early interactions illustrate that the pre-arrival phase is closely embedded within preceding processes and facilitates a seamless transition into the collaborative preparation of the port call.

As shown in Figure 7, the process begins with the Start Event '*Arrival notice*', which is triggered by the ship's port call announcement. This notification is typically initiated by the ship representative and transmitted via the P3C system to the involved actors. This is followed by the creation of the required framework agreements (Task: '*Drafting of framework agreements*'). These documents define the general conditions governing the cooperation between the ship and terminal operators. Once prepared, the respective contracts are sent to the relevant parties through the P3C system.

The process is followed by an Exclusive Gateway featuring the decision point '*Do the agreements meet the requirements?*'. This gateway assesses whether the drafted framework agreements comply with the requirements and interests of all parties involved. The requirements considered in this decision-making process relate primarily to operational, organisational, and regulatory aspects that are essential for a smooth and efficient port call.

Operational requirements include, for example, the precise coordination of arrival and berth times. Organisational requirements encompass the clear allocation of responsibilities and points of contact, as well as adherence to defined process steps and deadlines. Regulatory and legal requirements involve compliance with national and international regulations, the observance of safety and environmental standards, liability arrangements, and any other contractual obligations relevant to the port call.

In this way, the gateway ensures that the framework agreements systematically address all critical aspects of the port call and provide a foundation for a planned, efficient, and legally compliant execution of the process.

- In the event of a negative outcome (path ‘No’), a process for the coordination and revision of the contractual clauses is initiated. The relevant stakeholder on the port side communicates its requested amendments via the P3C system to the Ship Representative, who subsequently proposes a revised draft. This iterative procedure continues until mutual agreement between the parties is achieved.
- Once the contractual conditions have been accepted (path ‘Yes’), the revised contract is finalised and the process transitions into the execution phase.

Following successful agreement, a phase of parallel monitoring commences on both. In the BPMN model, this is represented by a Parallel Gateway, which initiates simultaneous monitoring processes on the ship and port sides (see Figure 8). Within this monitoring stage, each side includes an Exclusive Gateway containing the decision question ‘*Port side violations detected?*’ or ‘*Ship side violations detected?*’, respectively.

Potential violations that may occur during the contractual period can be categorised into operational, organisational, and regulatory types. Operational breaches may include, for example, delays in arrival or departure, as well as the unavailability of berths. Organisational breaches relate, for instance, to the failure to adhere to agreed process steps, lack of communication, or insufficient information exchange between the parties involved. Regulatory breaches may involve non-compliance with national or international regulations, safety and environmental standards, liability provisions, or other contractual obligations.

The identification and classification of such breaches is of central importance in order to initiate corrective measures in a timely manner, clarify responsibilities, and ensure compliance with the agreed standards within the port call process. In this way, the integrity of the process is maintained, supporting the planned, safe, and efficient execution of the port call.

- If no violations are detected on either side (path ‘No’), the process proceeds to the End Event ‘*Arrival at the port area*’, marking the successful completion of the pre-arrival phase.
- If deviations or violations are detected (path ‘Yes’), a task for the assessment and evaluation of the identified infringements is triggered. Subsequently, the affected parties are informed via the P3C system, and appropriate corrective measures are implemented.

After the completion of these measures, the process returns to the preceding monitoring phase to ensure continuous supervision and compliance with the agreed conditions and ultimately concludes with the End Event ‘*Arrival at the port area*’.

Figure 7 Pre-arrival - contracts and regulations layer (first part)

Figure 8 Pre-arrival - contracts and regulations layer (second part)

5.2.1.2 P3C Layer

The modelled sequence depicted in the Figures 9 and 10 begins with a Start Event on the ship side, specifically within the responsibility of the ship representative. This Start Event, labelled ‘Arrival notice’, serves as the initial trigger for the entire port arrival process (see Figure 9).

Within the project’s proposed procedure, the initial task is defined as ‘Gather initial port call data’. In this phase, the ship’s representative collects the essential baseline information related to the port call, including the ETA and ETD at berth. Building upon this, the project delineates a subsequent task in which the acquired data are systematically transmitted to the MSW by the ship’s representative. A harmonised, global approach to facilitating maritime traffic is of central importance for an efficient international shipping industry, as governed by the international FAL Convention.

On the port side, the process continues within the MSW lane. Here, the initial port call data is received (Task: ‘Receive initial port call data’). Immediately afterwards, data transfer, e.g., via API, is initiated to forward the information to the P3C, which acts as the central coordination point within the port’s operational structure.

Within the P3C lane, the next Task involves the *receipt and distribution of the initial port call data* (Task: ‘Receive and distribute initial port call data’). Based on these inputs and following the ship’s arrival in the *Port Passage Planning Area*, the relevant stakeholders develop a preliminary plan for the ship’s port arrival in the subsequent process. This plan includes the derivation of an RTA berth and RTA PBP (Task: ‘Obtain a preliminary schedule involving parties relevant to operations based on the initial port call data/ETA berth/ETD berth and derive an RTA berth and RTA PBP’).

These preliminary scheduling parameters are then disseminated to the ship side via the P3C in the Task ‘Distribute RTA berth and RTA PBP’ (see Figure 10). Upon receipt of the final RTA berth and RTA PBP, the ship’s representative (in this case: ship’s master, in coordination with the ship’s agent) uses the provided information to confirm the PTA berth and the corresponding PTA PBP. The confirmed final planning data are subsequently submitted to the P3C through the Task ‘Confirm and transmit PTA berth and PTA PBP’. Following this, the P3C receives and further distributes the finalised schedule.

In parallel, port-side resource monitoring is conducted to ensure operational readiness. Potential changes in the schedule, such as delays, berth availability, or operational constraints, may require adjustments to the initial plan. If such changes occur, a re-planning process is triggered to ensure smooth port operations.

This leads to the Exclusive Gateway ‘Are there any changes in the schedule?’:

- If changes are detected (path ‘Yes’), a revised RTA berth and updated RTA PBP are defined and resynchronised with the ship side.
- If no changes are identified (path ‘No’), the process proceeds directly to the End Event ‘Arrival at the port area’.

At the same time, the ship receives information about the agreed PTA so that it can adjust its speed if necessary. This results in monitoring on the ship side. This monitoring also culminates in the Exclusive Gateway ‘Are there any changes in the schedule?’:

- If no changes are identified (path 'No'), the process concludes with the same End Event, marking the ship's physical arrival within the designated port waters.
- However, in the event of schedule modifications (path 'Yes'), a new ETA berth is transmitted to the P3C, thereby initiating a renewed coordination cycle involving the revision of further time stamps.

Figure 9 Pre-arrival - P3C layer (first part)

Figure 10 Pre-arrival - P3C layer (second part)

5.2.1.3 Operations layer

The illustrated process in Figure 11 outlines the initial stages of a port call from the ship's perspective. It begins with the Start Event labelled 'Arrival notice' which triggers the subsequent activities. Immediately following this, the process continues with the Task 'Sail to the port', representing the ship's transit towards the port.

Subsequently, the process reaches an Exclusive Gateway, posing the decision point 'Planned stop?'. This step determines whether the ship is scheduled to make a stop at the anchorage/waiting area/drift area before entering the port.

- If no stop is planned (path 'No'), the process proceeds directly to the End Event 'Arrival at the port area'.
- If a stop is planned (path 'Yes'), the Task 'Coordination of further processes with the port' can be carried out as an additional measure to facilitate the process flow. The ship's representative coordinates with the port on subsequent steps, such as berth allocation, NSP/SSP/CSP arrangements, or other operational measures. This path also concludes with the End Event 'Arrival at the port area'.

Figure 11 Pre-arrival - operations layer

5.2.2 Port arrival

5.2.2.1 Contracts and regulations layer

The subsequent phase begins with the Start Event 'Arrival at the port area' and marks the transition from the preparatory pre-arrival phase to the actual arrival phase (see Figure 12). During this stage, parallel tasks are carried out to coordinate the ship's arrival and the subsequent port activities.

At the outset, two essential tasks are executed in parallel. Firstly, the coordination and establishment of the required agreements with the involved service providers for arrival, departure and berth visit take place (Task: 'Establish agreements with required service providers

for arrival, departure and berth visit'). These agreements define the fundamental services and responsibilities of the participating service providers, such as NSP, SSP and CSP, and serve to ensure the organisational agreements for the ship's handling operations. In parallel, the agreed arrangements are transmitted via the P3C system to the corresponding service providers (Task: 'Receiving and transmitting the necessary agreements to the relevant service providers') (see Figure 13). Subsequently, a content review and validation of these agreements are performed (Task: 'Validation of the agreements') to ensure that the provided information meets the operational requirements and the legal framework applicable to each service provider. This is followed by an Exclusive Gateway incorporating the decision point 'Do the content meet the requirements?'

- If the agreements do not meet the specified requirements (path 'No'), an alignment procedure is initiated (Task: 'Commence alignment procedure and propose adjustments'). The P3C system transmits the modification requests of the respective stakeholders to the Ship Representative, who makes the necessary adjustments and resubmits the revised agreements to the service providers for further validation (Task: 'Validation of the agreements').
- If the content meets the requirements (path 'Yes'), all agreements are formalised (Task: 'Formalisation of agreements'). At this stage, the agreements with the NSP for the arrival phase enter into force.

After the completion of these tasks, parallel monitoring processes are initiated on both the port and ship sides (Task: 'Monitor the fulfilment of the agreements during arrival'). In the BPMN model, these are represented by a Parallel Gateway (see Figure 14). During the monitoring phase, each side includes an Exclusive Gateway with the decision points 'Ship side violations detected?' and 'Port side violations detected?', respectively. Such violations may include deviations from the planned schedule, non-compliance with safety or operational procedures, incomplete or incorrect documentation, or other actions that could disrupt the smooth flow of operations in the port.

- If violations are detected (path 'Yes'), the necessary actions are examined and initiated (Task: 'Check actions and inform P3C'). The P3C system handles the communication and forwards information regarding the detected violations and the corresponding corrective measures to the affected parties (Task: 'Reception and forwarding of the violation and the corresponding actions'). The monitoring phase then continues.
- If no violations are detected (path 'No'), both monitoring processes are merged again through a Parallel Gateway.

Concurrently with the activities on the ship side, immediately following the initiating event of 'Arrival at the port area', an assessment is conducted to determine whether entry is permitted by the competent authorities. This assessment is represented by an Exclusive Gateway featuring the decision point 'Entry permitted?' which governs the authorisation to access the port area. Should entry be denied, access to the port is consequently prohibited.

- If the ship's entry is not authorised (path 'No'), the process for this branch terminates with the exclusion of the ship's arrival.

- If entry is granted (path ‘Yes’), the release information is forwarded via the P3C system to the relevant actors, thereby enabling the subsequent port operations. This sequence also ends in a Parallel Gateway.

Once both process branches reach the Parallel Gateway, the workflows are merged. The process concludes with the End Event ‘*Arrival at the berth*’, marking the successful completion of the arrival phase and the beginning of the berthing period.

Figure 12 Port arrival - contracts and regulations layer (first part)

Figure 13 Port arrival - contracts and regulations layer (second part)

Figure 14 Port arrival - contracts and regulations layer (third part)

5.2.2.2 P3C Layer

As shown in Figure 15, the process begins in this phase with the Start Event *´Arrival at the port area´*. Upon approach, the ship formally announces its arrival via VHF. Consequently, the P3C receives the arrival notification and distributes this information to all relevant operational stakeholders within the port organisation. A central element of this process is the NOR, which serves as the official confirmation of the ship’s operational readiness. The NOR forms the basis for numerous subsequent processes in port operations and the shipping industry. For the NOR to be legally valid, certain requirements must be met: the ship must be at the agreed location, physically and legally ready for operations, and all necessary documentation must be complete. The NOR is submitted by the ship once these conditions are fulfilled and the ship is considered to have *´arrived´*. By recording port stay data in advance and submitting the formal NOR, it is ensured that the port arrival process can be initiated in a structured, traceable, and efficient manner.

Subsequently, the process continues with an Exclusive Gateway *´PTA PBP met?´*. Should this not be the case (path *´No´*), the P3C informs all relevant stakeholders of the deviation from the agreed schedule (Task: *´Notify relevant parties of changes in the schedule´*). As a result, a revised coordination process is initiated by all relevant stakeholders to determine updated values for both the RTA berth and the RTA PBP (Task: *´New alignment on RTA berth and RTA PBP´*). These revised time stamps are then forwarded by the P3C to the ship’s representative (Task: *´Distribute RTA berth and RTA PBP´*). Based on this input, the ship’s representative derives a new PTA for both the berth and the PBP and transmits these updated values back to the P3C, which subsequently disseminates the revised data across all operational units within the port system.

Following this, a continuous monitoring of resource availability and schedule alignment is conducted by the NSP (Task: *´Monitor resources: Share updates (if necessary)´*), leading into the second Exclusive Gateway *´Are there any changes in the schedule?´* (see Figure 16).

- If changes are identified (path *´Yes´*), the P3C communicates the relevant delays to all stakeholders and initiates another round of coordination to redefine the RTA berth and RTA PBP.
- If no deviations are observed (path *´No´*), the RTA berth is documented and made available to all involved parties (Task: *´Documentation and distribution of the RTA berth to all relevant parties´*). This process branch then concludes with the End Event *´Arrival at the berth´* (see Figure 17).

In contrast, if the initial Exclusive Gateway *´PTA PBP met?´* confirms that a PTA has already been established (path *´Yes´*), the P3C promptly informs all relevant parties of the maintained schedule, thereby enabling timely provision of the required services. In this context, the NSP receive the official instruction to commence their respective operations (see Figure 15). This branch also leads into the same Exclusive Gateway *´Are there any changes in the schedule?´* (see Figure 16).

- Should changes be detected (path *´Yes´*), the response mirrors the previously described procedure: The P3C communicates delays, coordinates new RTA values for berth and PBP, and updates the process accordingly.

- Conversely, if no schedule changes occur (path ‘No’), the ATA berth is recorded and shared, and the branch concludes with the same End Event ‘Arrival at the berth’.

In parallel, a request is issued to the CSP and SSP to provide ETS and ETC for the intended services (Task: ‘Provide an ETS/ETC for the requested services’). These estimates are received and consolidated by the P3C and subsequently forwarded to the ship’s representative (Task: ‘Receive and distribute the ETS/ETC’) (see Figure 17). Based on these Figures, the ship side returns an RTS and RTC to the P3C, which in turn relays this information back to the CSP and SSP. Using the RTS/RTC as a reference, the CSP and SSP derive the finalised PTS and PTC. These definitive time allocations are ultimately communicated to all relevant parties within the End Event ‘Receive and distribute the PTS/PTC’, thereby formally concluding the process.

Figure 15 Port arrival - P3C Layer (first part)

Figure 16 Port arrival - P3C Layer (second part)

Figure 17 Port arrival - P3C Layer (third part)

5.2.2.3 Operations layer

In the following, the operations layer is examined in greater detail with a focus on the port arrival process (see Figure 18). The process begins with the Start Event *´Arrival at the port area´*, which marks the ship’s arrival within the designated port waters. Immediately following this, an Exclusive Gateway evaluates whether there are any schedule changes on the ship’s side (*´Changes in the schedule (ship side)?´*). At this point, a decision is made as to whether the planned port call operation can proceed as intended.

If changes are detected (path *´Yes´*), the ship is first directed to a designated holding position (Task: *´Proceed to holding position´*). A holding position is a pre-defined location where a ship can temporarily remain when changes to the planned process are detected. In this position, the ship waits for authorization to proceed with the next step, and may, if necessary, temporarily anchor or drift offshore. From there, the process proceeds to another Exclusive Gateway *´Continue with the port call?´*, where it is determined whether the port call may now be continued.

- Should it be decided that the port call cannot yet proceed (path *´No´*), the process loops back to the Task *´Proceed to holding position´*. This cycle may repeat multiple times until the conditions necessary for continuation are met.
- Once a positive decision is reached (path *´Yes´*), the next step in the process is initiated: The ship begins waiting for the support of the NSP (Task: *´Wait for NSP´*).

In cases where no schedule changes are identified immediately upon arrival (path *´No´*), the process also transitions directly to the Task *´Wait for NSP´*.

At this point, the ship remains in a holding state until all operational preconditions for the continuation of the port call have been met.

Subsequently, the process passes through another Exclusive Gateway, labelled *´Changes in the schedule (port side)?´*, this time on the port side, where it is evaluated whether schedule changes have occurred on the part of the NSP. Such changes may arise, for example, due to unavailability of tugboats, pilots, or berth space.

- If changes on the port side are present (path *´Yes´*), the updated information is communicated via the P3C (Task: *´Communicate changes via the P3C´*). This is followed by a renewed decision process, which determines whether the port call can proceed – ensuring synchronisation between the ship and port actors.
- If no deviations are identified (path *´No´*), the NSP provides the requested nautical services (Task: *´Provide requested services´*).

Upon successful berthing (Task: *´Get berthed´*), the NSP-side Task *´End of operations and return to base´* is carried out, indicating that the involved operational units (e.g., tugs or pilot ships) return to their base of operations.

The process concludes with the End Event *´Arrival at the berth´*, which marks the successful completion of the ship’s berthing manoeuvre and the end of the port arrival phase. This represents a key milestone within the overall port call, after which terminal-side operations typically commence.

Figure 18 Port arrival - operations layer (first part)

5.2.3 Berth visit

5.2.3.1 *Contracts and regulations layer*

The berth-visit phase begins with the Start Event *Arrival at the berth* and directly follows the preceding process segment of the arrival phase (see Figure 19). With the commencement of this phase, the previously defined agreements between the CSP and SSP come into effect. These agreements regulate the services to be provided and the responsibilities of both parties during the berthing period and form the foundation for the subsequent monitoring and communication processes.

At the beginning, parallel monitoring processes are initiated on both the port and ship sides (Task: *Monitor the fulfilment of the agreements during berth visit*). In the BPMN model, this parallel execution is represented by a Parallel Gateway. The purpose of these processes is to ensure compliance with the contractually agreed services and behavioural obligations throughout the berthing period.

Within this monitoring phase, each side includes an Exclusive Gateway containing the decision point *Ship side violations detected?* or *Port side violations detected?*.

- If violations are detected (path *Yes*), appropriate measures are examined and initiated (Task: *Check actions and inform P3C*). The P3C system performs the communication function in this context and transmits information regarding the identified violations and the corresponding corrective actions to the affected parties (Task: *Reception and forwarding of the violation and the corresponding actions*). Once the measures have been implemented, the process returns to the monitoring phase to ensure continuous supervision.
- If no violations are detected on the port side (path *No*), the monitoring process for this branch concludes at a Parallel Gateway (see Figure 20).

On the ship side, a negative inspection result (path *No*) triggers the initiation of the departure procedure. The first step involves submitting a request for departure authorisation (Task: *Request port departure permit*). This request is transmitted by the P3C system to the competent authorities, followed by an Exclusive Gateway containing the decision point *Departure permitted?* (see Figure 20).

- If departure authorisation is not granted (path *No*), further coordination of the departure process is required and a new request cycle begins.
- If authorisation is granted (path *Yes*), the P3C system forwards the corresponding confirmation to the ship side and the process continues via a Parallel Gateway.

Once both parallel process branches, the port-side monitoring process and the ship-side monitoring and authorisation process, reach the Parallel Gateway, they are merged. The overall process of the berth-visit phase concludes with the End Event *Departure from the berth*, marking the successful completion of the berthing period and the release of the ship for departure.

Figure 19 Berth visit – contracts and regulations layer (first part)

Figure 20 Berth visit – contracts and regulations layer (second part)

5.2.3.2 P3C Layer

The process illustrated in Figure 21 begins on the ship side with the Start Event *Arrival at the berth*. Immediately following this event, the P3C executes the Task *Documentation and distribution of the ATA berth to all relevant parties*, ensuring that the ATA is communicated across all operational stakeholders.

In the subsequent Task *Monitor resources: Share updates (if necessary)*, the CSP and SSP monitor their respective resource availability to ensure that the required port services can be provided as scheduled. This operational context leads to an Exclusive Gateway *PTS met?*, which evaluates whether the PTS can be adhered to.

- If the PTS cannot be met (path *No*), the process transitions back to the port arrival phase, specifically restarting at the Task *Provide an ETS/ETC for requested services*, where a renewed coordination with the ship's representative is initiated to reassess service requirements. Departure (End Event: *Return to the Port arrival phase, starting at the Task Provide an ETS/ETC for requested services*). However, if a renewed agreement is not desired and the ship opts to depart due to the inability to maintain the agreed schedule, the process moves forward directly to the subsequent phase *Port departure* (End Event: *Proceed directly to the Port departure phase*).
- Conversely, if the PTS can be maintained (path *Yes*), the ship's representative proceeds with the Task *Announce departure*, formally initiating the departure process. As part of this announcement, the ETD berth is continuously updated based on the previously determined PTC and communicated to the P3C. The P3C, in turn, receives and disseminates this information to all relevant parties within the port (see Figure 22).

Following this, the stakeholders involved generate a preliminary departure schedule based on the ETD berth received (Task: *Obtain a preliminary schedule based on the updates*). This preliminary schedule is first sent to the P3C and subsequently forwarded to the ship's representative, who then determines and communicates PTD for both the berth and the PBP (Task: *Determine and transmit PTD berth and PTD PBP*). The P3C then distributes this updated information internally within the port organisation.

Throughout ongoing operations, the CSP and SSP continue to monitor their resources and provide updates where necessary (Task: *Monitor resources: Share updates (if necessary)*). This leads to another decision point represented by the Exclusive Gateway *Are there any changes in the schedule?*.

- If significant schedule deviations are identified (path *Yes*), the process initiates a re-alignment phase, beginning with the Task *New alignment on RTD berth and RTD PBP*, where the RTD for both berth and PBP is renegotiated and updated accordingly.
- If no such deviations are observed (path *No*), and operations proceed according to the agreed schedule, the process concludes with the End Event *Departure from the berth*.

Figure 21 Berth visit - P3C layer (first part)

Figure 22 Berth visit - P3C layer (second part)

5.2.3.3 Operations layer

The process depicted in Figure 23 begins with the ship's arrival at the berth, which is initiated by the Start Event '*Arrival at the berth*'. This event signifies the formal commencement of port-side operations from the ship's perspective. Immediately following this, the process advances to an initial decision point represented by the Exclusive Gateway '*Changes to the schedule (ship side)?*', which examines whether any deviations from the pre-established schedule have occurred on the ship side.

If no such deviations are identified (path '*No*'), the process continues on the port side. At this stage, a similar assessment is conducted through the second Exclusive Gateway '*Changes to the schedule (port side)?*', which evaluates whether the service providers can adhere to the planned schedule.

Should the schedule remain unaffected (path '*No*'), the requested services are delivered as initially arranged (Task: '*Provide requested services*'). Concurrently, the ship receives the agreed services (Task: '*Get services*'), after which port-side operations are finalised (Task: '*End of operations*'), and the process concludes with the End Event '*Departure from the berth*'.

However, if it is determined that schedule deviations have occurred on either the port or ship side (path '*Yes*'), the process branches to an additional decision point that defines the subsequent course of action. At this juncture, the ship is presented with two possible responses:

1. The ship may choose to depart the port prematurely (Task: '*Depart from the port*'), which leads directly to the End Event '*Departure from the berth*'. This may occur when agreed-upon services are not made available in a timely manner, leading to avoidable idle time at berth. Such delays, caused by the unavailability of cargo handling equipment, personnel shortages, technical disruptions, or regulatory obstacles, for instance, can generate additional costs and disrupt the ship's schedule. To minimise economic losses and maintain operational efficiency, the ship seeks to depart the port as promptly as possible.
2. Alternatively, it may opt to remain at berth and wait until service provision is resumed (Task: '*Wait until services are resumed*'). Once services become available again, they are provided accordingly, allowing the process to continue towards its standard conclusion at the End Event '*Departure from the berth*'.

Figure 23 Berth visit - operations layer

5.2.4 Port departure

5.2.4.1 *Contracts regulations layer*

As shown in Figure 24, the port departure phase constitutes the final segment of the port call process and commences with the Start Event *'Departure from the berth'*. At the onset of this phase, the previously established agreements and service arrangements with the NSP governing the ship's departure come into effect. These agreements define the organisational, safety-related, and operational measures designed to ensure the smooth and efficient execution of the port departure.

At the beginning of this phase, parallel monitoring processes are initiated on both the port and ship sides (Task: *'Monitor the fulfilment of the agreements during departure'*). In the BPMN model, these parallel activities are represented by a Parallel Gateway. The purpose of the monitoring is to supervise adherence to the established agreements during the departure operation and to ensure that both the technical and contractual requirements are met.

Within these monitoring processes, each side employs an Exclusive Gateway featuring the decision question *'Ship side violations detected?'* or *'Port side violations detected?'* respectively.

- If violations are detected (path *'Yes'*), appropriate corrective actions are examined, coordinated, and initiated (Task: *'Check actions and inform P3C'*). In this context, the P3C receives and disseminates information regarding the identified violations and the corresponding corrective measures to the relevant parties (Task: *'Reception and forwarding of the violation and the corresponding actions'*). Once corrective actions have been completed, the monitoring phase resumes to continue ensuring compliance with the established agreements.
- If no violations are detected on either side (path *'No'*), the parallel monitoring processes are consolidated through a Parallel Gateway.

Once both paths converge at the Parallel Gateway, the overall process of this phase concludes with the End Event *'Departure from the port area'*. This End Event signifies the formal and operational completion of the port call process, as the ship has departed from the port area and transitioned into the subsequent navigation or transit phase.

Figure 24 Port departure – contracts regulations layer

5.2.4.2 P3C Layer

The process illustrated in Figure 25 begins with the Start Event ‘Departure from the berth’ on the ship side, marking the formal initiation of operational procedures associated with a ship’s departure from the port area. The central coordinating role on the ship side is assumed by the Ship Representative, who initiates and manages subsequent process steps in close coordination with the P3C.

The first operational step involves a decision gateway in the form of an Exclusive Gateway, posed with the question ‘PTD berth met?’, which assesses whether the PTD berth has been adhered to.

In the case of schedule conformity (path ‘Yes’), the P3C informs all relevant operational stakeholders about the provision of the required services at the scheduled time. Based on this, the NSPs receive the official order to commence operations.

This is followed by a second Exclusive Gateway, which evaluates whether any schedule deviations have occurred during the ongoing operations (‘Are there any changes in the schedule?’).

- If no deviations are detected (path ‘No’), the process concludes with the documentation and dissemination of the ATD berth (Task: ‘*Documentation and distribution of the ATD berth to all relevant parties*’). Subsequently, the process is formally completed through the End Event ‘*Departure from port area*’.
- In contrast, should deviations from the schedule be identified (path ‘Yes’), the P3C initiates a targeted communication process. As part of the Task ‘*Communicate changes in the schedule via P3C*’, all relevant parties are notified of the updated status.

If the PTD berth is not met (Exclusive Gateway: ‘*Are there any changes in the schedule?*’; path ‘no’), the P3C informs the relevant stakeholders of the schedule deviations (Task: ‘*Notify relevant parties of changes in the schedule*’). This leads to a renewed coordination step via the Task ‘*New alignment on RTD berth*’, during which a revised RTD berth is defined. The updated time stamp is transmitted to the ship side, where the ship representative determines a new PTD berth, which is then submitted to the P3C by the ship representative and subsequently distributed to all operational stakeholders (Task: ‘*Confirm and transmit PTD berth*’) (see Figure 26).

Following this, NSPs monitor the availability of their respective resources to ensure operational continuity (Task: ‘*Monitor resources: Share updates (if necessary)*’). Another Exclusive Gateway is used to examine whether any additional changes in the schedule have occurred (‘*Are there any changes in the schedule?*’).

- If further adjustments are required (path ‘Yes’), these updates are communicated back to the P3C, which redistributes the revised schedule data to all relevant stakeholders, initiating another alignment on RTD berth if necessary.
- Should no further changes be reported (path: ‘No’), the actual departure time is once again documented and communicated (Task: ‘*Documentation and distribution of the ATD berth to all relevant parties*’), thereby bringing the process to its conclusion with the End Event ‘*Departure from port area*’ (see Figure 26).

Figure 25 Port departure - P3C layer (first part)

Figure 26 Port departure - P3C layer (second part)

5.2.4.3 Operations layer

The process illustrated in Figure 27 commences on the ship side with the Start Event *´Departure from the berth´*, marking the initiation of the ship’s departure phase. Subsequently, the ship awaits the provision of services by the NSP (Task: *´Wait for NSP at berth´*).

Following this, a decision is made as to whether there are any changes to the schedule.

- If such changes occur (path *´Yes´*), they are communicated to the ship via the P3C (Task: *´Communicate changes via the P3C´*), after which the ship again waits for the NSP’s confirmation or service provision.
- If no changes are identified (path *´No´*), the port side proceeds to deliver the requested services (Task: *´Provide requested services´*).

Once all necessary operations have been completed, the ship undertakes the Task *´Get unberthed´*, during which it is released from its berth. This is followed by an Exclusive Gateway labelled *´Proceed to another berth?´*.

- Should the ship be required to move to another berth within the port area, it returns to the *´Port Arrival´* phase, thereby restarting the cycle.
- If no further berthing is required, the process continues with the Tasks *´End of operations and return to base´* and *´Sail out of the port area´*, representing the ship’s physical departure from the port area.

The process concludes with the End Event *´Departure from port area´*, signifying the completion of all port-related activities and the formal transition of the ship to the next navigational phase.

Figure 27 Port departure - operations layer

5.2.5 Strategies and Methods for the Implementation of the Blueprint

Approaches to the coordination of port calls constitute a key component for enhancing efficiency and promoting ecological optimization in maritime logistics. By integrating planning, communication, and monitoring tools, a structured and data-driven management of port arrivals becomes feasible. Central elements of this approach include the early definition of the PTA, the dynamic updating of the ETA and RTA, as well as the continuous tracking of ship positions. This combination ensures a high degree of responsiveness to external influencing factors while maintaining a stable and reliable planning foundation.

A major advantage of port call coordination strategies lies in their departure from the conventional ‘hurry up and wait’ paradigm toward a more systematic eco-steaming approach. In traditional operational models, ships often travel at maximum speed to meet predefined time windows, only to face delays upon arrival due to limited port resource availability. This practice leads to excessive fuel consumption and increased emissions. In contrast, the provision of reliable ETA data allows for anticipatory and demand-oriented speed adjustments, unlocking significant potential for both operational efficiency and environmental sustainability. Particularly during the final approach to port, frequent ETA revisions may be required due to meteorological conditions, technical disruptions, or operational reconfigurations. The key challenge lies in responding to such changes with flexibility, without compromising the stability and reliability of the overall process.

However, frequent or short-notice corrections of arrival times can result in what is referred to as ‘system nervousness’, a condition in which digital planning systems exhibit disproportionate sensitivity to minor changes. This can lead to coordination issues, inefficient allocation of resources, and a loss of trust among stakeholders. To counteract these effects, a structured change management process is necessary, based on clearly defined criteria and response mechanisms. Changes to scheduled time windows should be processed by the system only if justified by substantial reasons and if predefined threshold values are exceeded or undershot. This approach allows for the establishment of a robust planning framework that balances stability with the necessary degree of adaptability.

At the same time, the continuous validation of time-related information remains essential, for instance through automated comparison with AIS data or through regular reporting by shipping companies (e.g., Noon Reports). By separating informational updates from actionable triggers, the system can avoid unnecessary overload while remaining capable of responding effectively to critical developments. Such a structured change management regime, governed by transparent decision rules, supports the maintenance of stable operational planning and simultaneously increases flexibility in the face of unforeseen events. As a result, not only can port call efficiency be improved, but stakeholder confidence in digital planning systems can also be enhanced. Ultimately, both waiting times and emissions can be significantly reduced.

Various coordination mechanisms can enable optimized arrival management, ensuring that ships arrive as close as possible to the scheduled time. The avoidance of unnecessary idle times leads to more efficient resource utilization and reduced fuel consumption. At the same time, planning reliability is increased – an aspect of particular relevance in the context of complex and dynamic port operations. Furthermore, early communication and synchronized information flows contribute to the prevention of operational bottlenecks and support a more effective

utilization of available port infrastructure. The combination of these effects ultimately results in increased ecological sustainability and economic performance across maritime supply chains.

In the following sections of this study, specific instruments and coordination approaches are presented that support the practical implementation of the proposed blueprint within the framework of DYNAPORT, thereby enabling sustainable and efficient management of port calls. It is important to emphasise that the approaches outlined herein are not presented in a hierarchical order, nor is any one element assigned a higher priority. Rather, they form part of a holistic and flexible approach that integrates a variety of methods and strategies, the relevance and emphasis of which can be tailored to the specific requirements and contextual conditions of individual ports.

Depending on the level of technological development, existing infrastructure, and organisational structures, the implementation of individual measures may vary in scope and intensity. Ideally, however, all described elements can be integrated into a comprehensive and coherent concept that enables the coordinated and holistic realisation of the blueprint, thereby contributing to the sustainable optimisation of port operations.

Furthermore, it is important to stress that the proposed approach is not to be understood as final or immutable. On the contrary, it is intended to be continuously extended and further developed to accommodate future technological advancements, operational needs, and innovative concepts.

5.2.5.1 APIs

During the digital transformation of maritime supply chains, APIs are becoming increasingly important. They enable automated, structured and standardised communication between different IT systems, e.g., between shipping companies, port authorities, terminal operators and other players along the transport chain. Within the framework of the developed blueprint, APIs are considered a central tool for increasing efficiency and improving the coordination of port processes, especially when transmitting time-critical information such as the ETA.

APIs function as digital interfaces that facilitate real-time data exchange between systems. This capability forms the foundation for coordinated logistics, enabling enhanced synchronization between ships, terminals, and regulatory authorities. Within the context of port operations and maritime transport, APIs support, among other functions:

- the transmission of ETA/RTA data from the ship to the port, VTS information, route information,
- the exchange of information on berths, loading/unloading status or planned processes,
- integration into port call optimisation (PCO) systems.

The information available via APIs, how it is provided technically and in which systems it can be used depends heavily on the digital infrastructure and strategy of the respective port. Not all ports have the same level of maturity or standardisation approach, which has a direct impact on the scope and quality of API usage.

Despite their great potential, APIs pose various challenges in a maritime context, the relevance and solubility of which often depend on the individual port:

- **Data quality and reliability:**

The accuracy and timeliness of ETA data vary greatly. Without active quality assurance on the port side, unreliable data can hardly be corrected or validated.

— **Standardisation:**

There are often differences in the data models and API specifications used. While some ports already rely on international standards (e.g., International Association of Ports and Harbours (IAPH), United Nations Centre for Trade Facilitation and Electronic Business (UN/CEFACT)), others use individual or historically developed solutions, which makes interoperability difficult.

— **Governance and responsibilities:**

The organisation and responsibility for the operation, maintenance and further development of APIs is not uniformly regulated. In some ports, this is the responsibility of the port authority, while in others it is delegated to platform providers or external service providers.

— **Security and data protection aspects:**

The secure operation of APIs (e.g., through authentication, access control and encryption) depends heavily on the respective port operator and its IT security strategy.

— **Technological and organisational requirements:**

Smaller or less digitised ports do not always have the human or technical resources to efficiently implement and use APIs.

The effective use of APIs within the framework of the DYNAPORT blueprint requires several prerequisites, the implementation of which is largely within the sphere of influence of the respective ports. Accordingly, no universal solutions can be formulated, but the following measures can serve as adaptable guidelines:

— **Introduction of open, standardised interfaces:**

Depending on their initial situation, ports should switch to internationally recognised data models and API standards in the medium term. Where this is not feasible, interim solutions with convertible formats are conceivable.

— **Establish clear governance structures in the respective port:**

Responsibility for APIs should be clearly regulated in the local context. This can be done by the port operator itself, a central data platform or a cooperation model with IT service providers.

— **Integrate monitoring and quality assurance locally:**

Port-owned monitoring tools for monitoring data quality and interface availability help to continuously improve reliability, ideally in conjunction with feedback loops from users (e.g., terminals, shipping companies).

— **Build secure and scalable API architectures:**

The development of a secure, robust interface infrastructure is crucial, but its scope and complexity depend heavily on the resources available in the respective port.

— **Gradual introduction with support for smaller players:**

In mixed-structure port regions in particular, a step-by-step approach should be taken, involving smaller partners with low-threshold API access or accompanying training.

5.2.5.2 Port call protocols

In response to the increasing complexity of global supply chains and the associated need to make maritime transshipment processes efficient and transparent, standardised port call protocols have been developed and introduced in the DYNAPORT project to serve as a normative structure for describing and classifying port calls. These protocols are intended not only to improve communication between shipping companies, port authorities and terminals, but above all to enable a systematic reduction in operational uncertainties.

The definition and application of these port call protocols makes it possible to translate complex maritime arrival processes into recognisable patterns. They provide a normative framework that refers to the dimensions of terminal utilisation and berthing strategy, thus allowing a structured description of a wide variety of port arrival constellations. This classification forms the basis for a digitally supported, comparable and analysable representation of port calls, for example in the context of KPI systems, capacity planning or simulations for resource allocation.

The blueprint distinguishes between four basic port call protocols, which can be systematised along two axes (number of terminals involved and number of berths allocated):

— **Single Terminal, Single Berthing-Protocol (STSB-Protocol):**

The STSB protocol describes the simplest form of a port call. In this case, the ship calls at a single terminal and uses only one berth during its entire stay in port.

This configuration is typical for container ships or bulk carriers that load or unload their entire cargo at one location. It allows for a high degree of predictability and is ideal for the application of digitally supported coordinated arrival processes, extending beyond JIT concepts. The operational interfaces are minimal, which reduces coordination effort and friction losses. In practice, this is the standard model for many medium-sized container ports or specialised terminals.

— **Single Terminal, Multiple Berthing-Protocol (STMB-Protocol):**

In contrast to the STSB protocol, the STMB protocol describes a situation in which a ship must call at the same terminal but use several berths – either sequentially or overlapping.

This situation often occurs when the ship requires different handling points within a terminal for different types of cargo, or when operational restrictions (e.g., limited berth availability) necessitate relocation within the terminal. Although only one terminal is affected, the complexity of call planning increases significantly, particularly for resource coordination, pilot requirements and safety approvals for mooring manoeuvres. The planning and communication effort is noticeably higher than with STSB.

— **Multiple Terminals, Single Berthing-Protocol (MTSB-Protocol):**

In the MTSB protocol, a single berth is used to handle activities, even though several terminals are involved in the port call. This is typical in cases where, for example, a

combined handling concept (e.g., containers and general cargo) is used and several companies jointly serve or coordinate the berth.

Although the ship physically occupies only one location in the port, the operational complexity increases due to the large number of stakeholders involved. This constellation requires a sophisticated communication and planning infrastructure to avoid redundancies, delays or resource bottlenecks. A high level of data integration between the terminals involved is essential here.

— **Multiple Terminals, Multiple Berthing-Protocol (MTMB-Protocol):**

The most complex form of port call is described by the MTMB protocol. This involves calling at several terminals, with a separate berth being provided for each terminal if necessary. This can be done either sequentially, i.e. in several consecutive calls, or in combination with mooring manoeuvres within a short period of time.

This type of protocol is typical for large ships with a differentiated cargo structure, such as RoRo/LoLo combinations, cruise ships or multi-purpose freighters, which handle different types of cargo or passenger groups at specific terminals. The coordination challenge is particularly high in this case. In addition to operational challenges (e.g., in the areas of pilot coordination, tugboat requirements and crew logistics), precise synchronisation of all terminals is required to avoid capacity conflicts and inefficiencies.

The introduction of the four standardised port call protocols represents a significant step towards a structured, comparable and planning-oriented description of maritime port calls. They form the backbone for the digitalisation of port call management and make it possible to reduce operational complexity through semantic clarity. Furthermore, they form the basis for data-driven decision-making systems that enable proactive management of resources and capacities in port operations. At a time when global supply chains are becoming increasingly vulnerable to disruption and energy-efficient processes are becoming a necessity, these protocols make a significant contribution to the resilience and sustainability of international maritime transport.

Importantly, the project envisages that the selected protocol for port calls can be transmitted early (in the pre-arrival phase) via the MSW, provided that the applicable protocol can be determined at the start of the planning process for the port call. If this is not the case, the framework alternatively provides for the protocol to be transmitted at a later stage via the P3C, ensuring that the normative classification is provided consistently and in a timely manner, regardless of when it is finally known.

5.2.5.3 ETA monitoring and updating

Accurate prediction of ship arrivals is crucial for the organisation of modern port processes. To increase the reliability of ETAs and make operational processes more flexible, various digital methods can be used that complement each other and have a significant impact when combined.

One possible approach is the use of geofencing. This involves virtually demarcating specific geographical areas so that the entry and exit of ships into these zones can be automatically recorded. In addition, digital corridors can be used to represent predefined and monitored routes. These two methods offer the possibility of transparently and continuously tracking ship movements and identifying deviations from the planned schedule at an early stage. On this basis,

operational measures such as adjusting berth allocations or assigning waiting positions could be initiated.

In addition, there is the option of setting up virtual checkpoints that are defined along the route. These checkpoints serve as reference points along the route where it can be verified whether the ship is on schedule and the PTA is likely to be met. In this case, deviations would serve as indicators of possible delays and could be directly transferred to an updated RTA.

The Virtual Time of Arrival (VTA) can be used as a higher-level control element. In contrast to the static ETA, it represents a dynamically calculated arrival time that is continuously adjusted based on current position data, speeds, weather conditions, port schedules and traffic situations. The VTA could thus help to enable coordinated ship arrival, such as JIT arrivals, reduce waiting times and lower energy consumption in maritime transport.

Various information sources are available for calculating a VTA. In addition to the classic noon reports transmitted daily from the ship, real-time data from the AIS, weather and current reports, port and traffic information, and direct feedback from the ship's command can be considered. The combination of these data sources makes it possible to make forecasts not only more accurate but also more robust against unforeseen influences.

Overall, these methods open a wide range of possibilities for data-based control of port calls and better coordination of operational processes. Depending on the infrastructure, degree of digitalisation and strategic orientation of a port, individual elements can be implemented in a targeted manner or used in combination. The aim is always to increase planning reliability, use resources more efficiently, minimise waiting times and, at the same time, contribute to reducing emissions and decarbonising maritime supply chains.

5.2.5.4 Time slot allocation

Another key element is time slot-based arrival management, which is based on the PTA and plays a crucial role, particularly in the context of JIT-oriented ship arrivals. This is not a conventional slot booking system, in which ships actively reserve time slots, but rather a procedure in which the arrival time slot is indirectly defined by the port based on the previously agreed PTA.

With the confirmation of a PTA, a defined time slot for port access is implicitly linked to the time slot-based arrival management system, which serves as the basis for the operational control of the port call. It should be noted that the specific design and scope of this time slot must be determined individually by each port. Different operational conditions and infrastructure requirements mean that the flexibility and precision of the time slots may vary in order to optimally meet the respective requirements.

The reliability and punctuality of ship arrivals within the defined time window constitute a critical criterion for the effective implementation of coordinated arrival processes. Adherence to the PTA forms the basis for immediate port access and efficient handling operations.

To ensure predictable traffic and capacity management, the project framework stipulates that tolerance thresholds and their associated operational consequences may be defined flexibly and context-specifically. An illustrative configuration may be structured as follows:

- **Arrival within the tolerance threshold (e.g., ± 30 minutes):**
The ship is handled as initially planned, as the deviation is operationally negligible and does not compromise the allocation of resources.
- **Arrival with a moderate deviation (e.g., ± 60 minutes):**
Direct handling is provided only if the prevailing terminal and port utilisation permits. Otherwise, the ship is integrated into the standard waiting logic and assigned an adjusted handling time.
- **Arrival outside the permissible tolerance (substantially early or significantly late):**
The allocated slot expires, and the ship is required to proceed to a designated waiting position until a revised arrival time and corresponding time window can be issued.

The incorporation of such flexibly configurable rules ensures controlled traffic-flow management, prevents infrastructural overload, and supports the synchronisation of maritime arrivals with terminal operations. By systematically linking arrival discipline, tolerance parameters, and adaptive allocation mechanisms, this approach provides a robust governance instrument that enhances both operational stability and strategic planning capacity.

The targeted use of PTA-based arrival management pursues several strategic goals: increasing planning reliability, optimising resource utilisation (e.g., berths, handling equipment, personnel) and reducing unnecessary waiting times and the associated fuel consumption and emissions. Against the backdrop of international climate targets and increasing demands for the decarbonisation of maritime transport chains, this approach is becoming increasingly important.

Within the framework of the DYNAPORT project, PTA-based arrival management is understood as a central control element of data-driven, cooperative port management. It forms the functional basis for digitally integrated port call management and promotes vertical and horizontal coordination of all actors along the maritime supply chain. The integration of real-time data, such as ETA and RTA, enables continuous adjustment and refinement of arrival control.

Overall, PTA-based, time slot-supported arrival management is an essential tool for realising the overarching objectives of the DYNAPORT blueprint. It supports the development of a resilient, proactively controlled port ecosystem that enables efficient, environmentally friendly and reliable handling of ship calls at the operational level.

5.2.5.5 *Contractual and regulatory enablement*

One possible strategy to promote coordinated port arrivals is to adapt contractual and regulatory frameworks in a targeted manner to enable better operational alignment between ships, shipping companies, and port organisations. The objective of this strategy is to establish legal, organisational, and economic conditions that support flexible, transparent, and energy-efficient arrival planning, for instance through JIT concepts.

A central focal point of this strategy lies in the design of charter and transport contracts. Traditionally, such agreements contain clauses obliging ships to maintain a minimum speed or to proceed to the port as early as possible. These provisions, however, contradict modern operational strategies such as so-called *eco-steaming*, in which ship speed and energy consumption are dynamically adjusted to the expected availability of port services. A viable strategic approach is therefore to revise contractual frameworks in such a way that they allow for

flexible and cooperative voyage management. New contractual models could explicitly permit variable speed profiles and provide legal certainty for operational coordination with P3C.

In this context, the JIT arrival clauses, developed by BIMCO, provides an important reference framework. This clause enables charterers and owners to agree jointly on an optimised time of arrival that facilitates an energy-efficient voyage and a coordinated port call, without prejudicing the rights and obligations of either party with respect to cargo, speed, or waiting time. The integration of such JIT clauses into charter agreements establishes a legal foundation for institutionalising operational flexibility while safeguarding the economic security of both contracting parties. By implementing the BIMCO clauses, the necessary synchronisation between ship operations, port logistics, and service availability can be achieved, thereby significantly enhancing operational efficiency and reducing fuel consumption. This allows shipping companies to operate more energy-efficiently without violating contractual obligations or incurring financial disadvantages. (cf. BIMCO 2021)

Equally important is the promotion of a seamless exchange of information between ship and shore. Coordinated arrival planning requires that operational data, such as ship position, estimated time of arrival, and service requirements, be shared in a standardised format and in real time. Such transparency calls for clear legal and organisational frameworks that ensure data security, confidentiality, and interoperability. A meaningful strategic measure could be to support information flows through binding guidelines that institutionalise data exchange while safeguarding sensitive information. This would enable shipping companies and port authorities to respond jointly to current operational developments and make timely adjustments to the arrival process.

In addition, the introduction of economic incentives can encourage participation in coordinated arrival processes. Current practices sometimes create economic disincentives, such as demurrage or detention arrangements, which may unintentionally reward delays. An alternative strategy would be to adapt existing remuneration and cost-sharing models so that efficient and schedule-compliant behaviour is rewarded. Ships actively participating in JIT arrival planning could, for example, benefit from reduced port fees, prioritised berth allocations, or accelerated service provision. This would create an economic incentive to participate in coordinated arrival strategies and thus enhance overall operational efficiency.

On the port side, complementary measures can also be taken to improve the efficiency and predictability of arrivals. Port authorities and terminal operators could establish a binding system for queue and slot management that prioritises arrivals in coordination with shipping companies and proactively mitigates conflicts over limited resources (see also Chapter 5.2.5.4). The targeted prioritisation of ships with confirmed arrival windows could contribute to stabilising overall port operations. In addition, service-level agreements should ensure that all relevant services, such as pilotage, cargo handling, bunkering, and waste management, are reliably available within the scheduled time frame.

In the long term, this strategy can only be successful if it is economically viable and provides tangible benefits to all parties involved. Consequently, all regulatory and contractual adjustments should be accompanied by a fair distribution of costs and benefits. The overarching objective is to create a shared basis of responsibility that promotes cooperation and strengthens the resilience and efficiency of the maritime supply chain.

Overall, this strategy offers the potential to establish the foundation for coordinated port arrivals through targeted contractual, regulatory, and organisational measures. The integration of international standard clauses, such as the BIMCO JIT arrival clauses, can serve as a key lever to reduce legal uncertainty and facilitate the practical implementation of such approaches. In doing so, transparency, efficiency, and sustainability in maritime transport are enhanced, contributing significantly to the decarbonisation and modernisation of global shipping and port operations.

6 Conclusion and Outlook

This chapter provides an overall summary of the work carried out within *Task 2.1 – Blueprint for Integrated Port Cooperation* and places the main findings in the broader context of the project. It outlines the key insights and experiences gained throughout the task and reflects on the extent to which the initial objectives have been addressed. Furthermore, it offers a concise overview of the main outcomes and observations emerging from the activities conducted so far. The chapter concludes with an outlook on the next steps foreseen for the continuation and further development of the results in upcoming project phases. Overall, it aims to summarise the progress achieved to date and to provide a perspective on future directions within the wider project framework.

6.1 Summary of T2.1

The work carried out under *T2.1 – Blueprint for Integrated Port Cooperation* represents an important contribution to the development of a systematic and transferable framework for improving port processes. The objective was to analyse the collaboration among the various actors within the port ecosystem, including port authorities, terminal operators, shipping agents, logistics service providers and public institutions, and to identify potential approaches for enhanced coordination and information exchange.

The findings of the analysis indicate that insufficient synchronisation among the involved actors can lead to significant efficiency losses within port operations. Divergent organisational structures, differing interests and heterogeneous technical standards often hinder coordinated planning and execution of logistic activities. This is particularly evident in relation to the alignment of ship arrival times, which serve as a central reference point for all subsequent operations in the port. Delays or short-notice changes in this respect tend to cause cascading effects, increasing both operational costs and environmental impacts.

A central focus of the study was therefore the identification of measures that could support the *early provision and reliability of arrival information*. Such measures form the basis for more accurate resource allocation, better utilisation of terminal capacities and greater transparency in communication among stakeholders. Furthermore, the study identified processes in which contractual and organisational frameworks may limit flexibility and cooperation. These constraints often result from unclear responsibilities, insufficient data availability or a lack of standardised information interfaces.

The blueprint concept developed within this task seeks to address the identified challenges through a structured and transferable approach. It considers both the functional processes within ports and their interfaces with wider logistic networks. The characteristic differences among port types, such as container, ferry or multipurpose ports, are examined as a first step to derive potential approaches for improved cooperation mechanisms. The blueprint is intended to serve as a reference framework that helps to better understand, assess and, where appropriate, further develop collaborative processes within and across institutional and geographical boundaries.

A major added value of this work lies in its integrative perspective. It connects empirical insights from participating ports with ongoing research and development activities within the overall project, as well as with external initiatives such as ITPCO, DCSA and other European

standardisation efforts. This alignment helps to avoid redundancies and fosters synergies for future demonstration and implementation phases. The results obtained under this task therefore provide not only scientific insights but also a practical foundation for the continued development of port cooperation strategies.

In addition, the blueprint forms a conceptual basis for subsequent work packages, particularly regarding the definition of suitable KPIs for measuring and evaluating progress. These indicators will enable transparent quantification of the effects in terms of efficiency, economic viability, environmental sustainability and social impact. Combined with the forthcoming demonstration activities, they will provide verifiable evidence of practical applicability and facilitate knowledge transfer to other European port environments.

In the longer term, the results of *T2.1* have the potential to support a sustainable transformation of port logistics. By promoting a more data-driven, digitally supported and collaborative operational model, ports can improve their efficiency while simultaneously contributing to broader environmental and societal objectives. Enhanced communication structures and decision-making processes can reduce waiting times, energy consumption and emissions, thereby aligning with European ambitions for sustainability, digitalisation and competitiveness.

In summary, the approaches developed under this task establish a solid foundation for more integrated, transparent and resilient port cooperation. The resulting blueprint document will serve as a key reference for planning future demonstration activities, identifying best practices and supporting both policy and industry decision-making. Consequently, *T2.1* makes a significant contribution to improving the efficiency, sustainability and long-term competitiveness of the European port sector.

6.2 Overall findings and critical reflection

The analyses and conceptual developments, carried out under *T2.1 – Blueprint for Integrated Port Cooperation*, have generated significant insights that highlight both the complexity and the transformative potential of improved coordination within the port ecosystem. The developed blueprint aims to establish structural and procedural foundations for enhanced collaboration among the various stakeholders, thereby unlocking efficiency gains, increasing transparency, and contributing to more sustainable port logistics.

At the core of the investigation was the question of how port processes, particularly those related to ship arrivals, can be coordinated to enable more precise planning and more reliable execution of logistical operations. The findings clearly demonstrate that a lack of synchronisation between different actors frequently leads to operational disruptions. Poor communication regarding ETAs, especially when subject to short-term changes, can adversely affect the entire logistics chain within the port. The consequences include prolonged berth occupancy, inefficient resource utilisation, increased operational costs, and a heightened environmental footprint. The underlying causes of these challenges are not merely technical in nature but often stem from institutional fragmentation, the absence of standardisation, and insufficient alignment of commercial interests.

To address these issues, *T2.1* proposed a range of methodological and technical instruments. Among these were standardised APIs designed to enable automated and interoperable real-time data exchange between heterogeneous IT systems. In addition, structured port call protocols

were developed to capture and analyse port visits in terms of their procedural logic and resource demands. Complementary measures included procedures for continuous monitoring and updating of ETAs, as well as a time allocation concept that defines operational thresholds for when a ship is considered "on time" or "delayed". This concept is especially relevant for implementing JIT arrivals, which require the coordination of arrival times to minimise waiting periods and ensure optimal preparation of shore-side logistics.

However, a more detailed examination reveals that the successful implementation of such concepts requires much more than technological solutions alone. One of the key challenges lies in the contractual relationships between the involved actors. Traditional charter party agreements and operational arrangements often lack the flexibility needed to allow for dynamic scheduling and speed adjustments by shipping companies. The economic risks associated with missed handling opportunities or additional costs due to delays make it difficult for stakeholders to adopt adaptive arrival strategies. In this context, new contractual instruments have the potential to expand the scope for collaboration and operational synchronisation.

A notable example is the JIT Arrival Clause developed by BIMCO, which can be added to existing charter agreements. This clause allows shipowners, in coordination with the port and based on shared planning assumptions, to regulate ship speed so that arrival occurs at a mutually agreed and operationally efficient time. The clause not only introduces new possibilities for voyage optimisation but also provides mechanisms for economic compensation, thus fairly distributing any potential disadvantages. Such provisions represent an important step towards the legal formalisation of coordinated arrival planning and create incentives for active participation in JIT-based cooperation.

Nonetheless, the analysis also reveals that the practical application of such clauses remains limited. Many stakeholders continue to rely on conventional contract models that make little allowance for adjusted arrival planning. The implementation of JIT operational models is therefore not merely a technical matter but also a contractual and institutional challenge. Achieving meaningful progress in this area will require clear allocation of responsibilities, binding communication processes, and a shared understanding of risks and benefits. In this context, it becomes apparent that technical standardisation and contractual harmonisation must be seen as complementary elements in enabling an effective and sustainable transformation of port operations.

Another key issue concerns the availability, quality, and usability of relevant data. The developed blueprint assumes that critical information such as arrival times, berth assignments, and resource planning data is available in a timely, complete, and standardised form. However, in practice, significant disparities exist in terms of data architecture, system interoperability, and the willingness to share operational data. Many actors operate under competitive market conditions that discourage open data exchange, while legal uncertainties and data protection regulations further limit access to and use of information. Addressing these challenges requires not only technical tools such as standardised interfaces, but also governance frameworks that institutionalise data management, clarify responsibilities, and foster trust among stakeholders.

The blueprint's flexibility, which allows adaptation to different port types and regional conditions, is generally viewed as a strength. It accommodates diverse infrastructural and organisational configurations, thereby supporting realistic and context-sensitive implementation. However, this flexibility also entails certain challenges. Without at least partial standardisation, there is a

risk that the blueprint remains a theoretical construct whose practical applicability is overly dependent on specific local circumstances.

In summary, the insights gained through *T2.1* make a valuable contribution to the ongoing discourse on the future of port logistics. The analysis underscores the need to consider technological innovation, organisational coordination, and contractual frameworks as interdependent components. The developed blueprint offers a practical reference model that can be used to identify best practices, define performance indicators, and design new modes of cooperation. However, the long-term impact of the approach will depend on the extent to which it succeeds in stimulating and institutionalising not only technical, but also legal and organisational innovation processes.

6.3 Achievements

The results of *T2.1* represent a pivotal milestone within the overall project and constitute a significant advancement in the development of integrated cooperation processes in European seaports. The developed blueprint provides a robust, practice-oriented and scientifically grounded reference structure that goes beyond purely technical optimisation and equally incorporates institutional, organisational and strategic dimensions. The objective was to design a model that strengthens collaboration among the various stakeholder groups involved in port call processes, while maintaining sufficient flexibility to be applicable across different port types, infrastructural settings and regional contexts.

The blueprint was deliberately conceived as a dynamic and adaptive reference model, maintaining conceptual coherence while allowing contextual adaptation. This flexibility enables its integration into a wide range of ports and facilitates alignment with differing levels of digital and organisational maturity. Through close cooperation with industry partners, particularly through table-top exercises and stakeholder dialogues, the blueprint was continuously validated and refined to ensure operational relevance. Moreover, alignment with the EU sister project *MISSION* ensures complementary and coherent development across project interfaces and fosters harmonisation with ongoing innovation initiatives.

A key focus of Work Package T2.1 was the development and integration of strategies for coordinated port calls, particularly concerning the implementation of JIT arrival concepts. These strategies aim to synchronise ship movements, port resources and downstream logistics in order to minimise waiting times, enhance resource efficiency and reduce greenhouse gas emissions. The blueprint integrates these strategic elements on several complementary levels:

- Operationally, through the standardisation of information flows and the continuous transmission of reliable ETA data to enable anticipatory planning decisions;
- Coordinatively, through the establishment of joint planning and decision-making mechanisms among port authorities, terminal operators, shipping lines and other stakeholders;
- Organisationally, through the definition of clear communication structures, roles and responsibilities to ensure transparent and resilient management of port call operations.

These integrative strategies lay the foundation for a data-driven and collaborative management of port operations. They foster transparency and trust among stakeholders and enable dynamic

adaptation to changing conditions, such as weather events, capacity fluctuations or supply chain disruptions.

Furthermore, *T2.1* deliberately pursued an application-oriented approach that distinguishes itself from existing idealised models, such as those proposed by the ITPCO or the DCSA. The focus was not merely on modelling an idealised port call but on systematically accounting for real operational conditions and potential sources of disruption. Accordingly, the blueprint explicitly addresses common challenges encountered in daily port operations, including weather-related delays, technical failures, short-notice resource constraints and supply chain bottlenecks. This realistic perspective has been instrumental in developing a robust and operationally relevant reference model that reflects the inherent complexity of port processes and provides actionable pathways for managing uncertainty.

By integrating such uncertainties and disturbance factors, the blueprint not only supports the validation of theoretical assumptions but also delivers concrete options for addressing operational deviations. Consequently, it transcends classical optimisation models by providing guidance not only for the ideal coordination of port calls but also for the institutional and organisational embedding of resilience and flexibility. This ensures that the developed strategies remain effective not only under optimal conditions but also within dynamic, complex and disruption-prone environments.

In addition, *T2.1* established the conceptual foundations for the development of KPIs that enable a holistic assessment of the impact of integrated cooperation models. These indicators capture operational efficiency, economic viability, environmental sustainability and social implications alike. Their application facilitates evidence-based evaluation of progress achieved within the demonstration activities and ensures the transferability of the blueprint to different port contexts.

Overall, Task *T2.1* provides a solid basis for the sustainable transformation of port logistics processes. The combination of data-driven, digitally supported and cooperative operational models opens new perspectives for more efficient, transparent and resilient maritime supply chains. The blueprint functions not merely as a technical planning tool but as a learning and adaptive system that evolves through interaction with involved stakeholders. Its strength lies in the combination of scientific rigour, practical applicability, contextual adaptability and strategic coherence. In doing so, *T2.1* makes a substantial contribution to the implementation of coordinated and sustainable port calls and directly supports the overarching objectives of the European Union in the fields of sustainability, digitalisation, energy efficiency and competitiveness.

6.4 Next steps

In the forthcoming project phase, the focus will be on demonstrating the results developed under *T2.1* through practical implementation scenarios. The aim is to assess whether the developed blueprint is not only theoretically robust but also practically applicable and reliable when implemented within a simulation of real-world port operations.

A central role is played by the DYNAPORT demonstrators associated with the blueprint. These demonstrators enable systematic testing of selected aspects of the blueprint under realistic conditions, facilitate the analysis of interactions between stakeholders, IT systems, and

operational processes, and provide insights into the model's practical applicability and flexibility. In this way, they contribute significantly to validating the robustness of the blueprint and provide empirically grounded evidence regarding its transferability to other port contexts.

Concurrently, as part of Deliverable *T6.2 – Integrated Simulation and KPI Development*, a discrete-event simulation model is being developed for a medium to large port scenario. The objective is to quantify the overall benefits and assess the impacts of the blueprint. Key performance indicators are being established to evaluate the performance of the enhanced port and ship coordination system, covering aspects such as emissions, safety, and port efficiency. Simulation activities are being advanced continuously to allow iterative refinement and adaptation based on emerging insights. Complementarily, an *impact assessment (T6.3)* provides empirical evidence of the blueprint's practical benefits.

An additional key aspect is the alignment with European standardisation initiatives such as ITPCO and the PCO Network, to leverage synergies, avoid redundancies, and ensure compatibility with international developments. In the long term, the validation of the draft could also form the basis for potential standardisation. By demonstrating its effectiveness in diverse port environments and continuously assessing its practical applicability, a robust foundation can be established for recognising the draft as a reference framework.

Moreover, based on the consultations conducted throughout the validation process, further targeted adjustments may be undertaken to develop an even more refined and contextually appropriate blueprint. Feedback from the participating stakeholders enables a critical reflection on existing elements and supports their systematic enhancement. In this way, an advanced and upgraded version of the submitted blueprint can be produced that is more closely aligned with operational requirements while simultaneously offering stronger compatibility with current and future standardisation efforts.

Emphasis is also placed on dissemination, recommendations, and outreach. The objective is to systematically communicate the acquired knowledge, best practices, and derived recommendations to relevant stakeholders, decision-makers, and the professional community. This includes presentations at national and international workshops and conferences, as well as publications in scientific journals. Additional formats, such as lectures at the Technical University of Hamburg, are employed to facilitate targeted knowledge transfer.

Overall, the validation process aims to demonstrate the blueprint's performance under realistic conditions, confirm its strengths, and identify potential areas for improvement. This approach ensures that the blueprint is not only theoretically robust but also operationally effective, delivering measurable value and contributing to more efficient, sustainable, and resilient port operations across Europe. Alignment with European standardisation processes further enhances the potential to achieve sector-wide improvements beyond local optimisations.

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D2.2 Blueprint of port call processes – Appendix

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Executive Summary

In the present blueprint of the DYNAPORT project, the underlying business process model is represented using Business Process Model and Notation (BPMN). Owing to the complexity and level of detail inherent in the model, a fully legible representation within the main document can only be achieved to a limited extent. For reasons of page economy and formal document structure, the embedded visualisation is presented in a reduced format, which may affect the readability of individual process elements and, in some cases, disrupt the continuity of reading.

To address this limitation, the present supplementary document has been developed. It provides enlarged and detailed representations of the BPMN model, thereby enabling a more precise examination of process logic, event sequences, and role- and system-based interactions. The appendix thus serves as an extended reference for readers requiring enhanced procedural transparency or a more rigorous technical validation of the model.

At the same time, the BPMN representation has been deliberately retained within the main document. In its condensed form, it supports a general understanding of the described processes and offers visual orientation that complements the accompanying textual explanations. Embedding the model within the main body of the text facilitates the illustration of conceptual relationships and situates the descriptive content within a coherent structural framework, without materially affecting the document's length or readability.

The combination of an integrated overview and a more detailed exposition in the appendix contributes to a balanced and coherent document structure. This approach accommodates both the requirement for a concise and consistent presentation within the blueprint and the need for a more in-depth consideration of the process model. The appendix should therefore be understood as a complementary component that enhances comprehensibility and supports a differentiated engagement with the BPMN model.

1 Appendices

1.1 Appendix A: Pre-arrival – contracts and regulations layer

1.2 Appendix B: Port arrival – contracts and regulations layer

1.3 Appendix C: Berth visit – contracts and regulations layer

1.4 Appendix D: Port departure – contracts and regulations layer

1.5 Appendix E: Pre-arrival – P3C layer

1.6 Appendix F: Port arrival – P3C layer

1.7 Appendix G: Berth visit – P3C layer

1.8 Appendix H: Port departure – P3C layer

1.9 Appendix I: Pre-arrival – operations layer

1.10 Appendix J: Port arrival – operations layer

1.11 Appendix K: Berth visit – operations layer

1.12 Appendix L: Port departure – operations layer

